

REINCARNATE

D3.1 – Circular decision-making for adaptive refurbishment and renovation of real estate assets

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D 3.1 Circular decision-making for adaptive refurbishment and renovation of real estate assets

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Abstract

This report introduces a comprehensive decision-making framework designed to guide asset managers and building owners in the adaptive refurbishment and renovation of real estate assets. The framework, developed within the Reincarnate project, leverages circular adaptive reuse scenarios to enhance sustainability in the construction sector. It consists of three decision-making levels: the first level establishes the initial intervention direction; the second level develops and decides on specific reuse scenarios; and the third level selects the most appropriate End-of-Life strategy for building products. This structured approach aims to address the challenges of functional obsolescence by providing clear guidelines for interventions, whether they involve renovation, adaptive reuse, or deconstruction, with an emphasis on circular economy principles. The methodologies presented are primarily theoretical, with future practical testing planned to validate the findings. This framework is poised to significantly advance circular economy practices by integrating theoretical knowledge with practical applications, ultimately contributing to the reduction of construction and demolition waste and the extension of building lifespans.

Keywords

Circular Decision-Making; Adaptive Reuse; Circular Economy; Adaptive Reuse Process; Scenario Development

Revisions

Version	Submission date	Comments	Author
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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
DoA	Description of Action
TRL	Technical Readiness Level
CP-IM	Circular Potential Information Management
CDW	Construction and Demolition Waste
AR	Adaptive Reuse
MCDM	Multi-criteria Decision-making
EoL	End-of-Life
AHP	Analytical Hierarchy Process
CIB	Cross-Impact Balance
CBA	Circular Building Adaptability
CR	Consistency Ratio
CI	Consistency Index
RI	Random Index
TOPSIS	Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution
FPIS	Fuzzy Positive Ideal Solution
FNIS	Fuzzy Negative Ideal Solution
CC	Closeness Coefficient

Reincarnate project

The average lifespan of a building is 39 years — in Europe, it is only 25-30 years — and the main reason for demolition is obsolescence. This is why there is a large amount of construction and demolition waste (CDW) — representing approximately 25-30% of all waste in Europe —, in addition to that generated in current construction works.

The recycling rate for CDW is relatively high (above 75%). This activity generated \$126.89 billion in 2019 — Europe contributed the largest share, almost two-fifths of the total global market — and is projected to reach \$149.19 billion by 2027. Unfortunately, many of the most valuable materials in CDW cannot be meaningfully separated and end up in landfills.

This helps to get an idea of the efficiency potential for climate neutrality that exists in construction.

Reincarnate aims at advancing circular economy practices within the European construction industry and enabling to significantly maximize the life cycle of buildings, construction products, and materials, reduce CDW by 80%, increase the reusability of buildings, construction products, and materials and, as a result, lower the sector's emissions by 70%.

As a result of these actions, Reincarnate will significantly advance circular economy practices within the European construction industry.

First, it will create a Circular Potential Information Management (CP-IM) platform and a set of innovations to use it. These solutions will draw upon emerging digital technologies, such as digital twin representation, artificial intelligence, and robotic automation.

3 empirically proven social science insights will allow fostering widespread adoption of reused high-quality construction products and materials, and business eco-system development frameworks to combine actors within sustainable value chains. All innovations will be demonstrated on eleven selected real-world projects and value chains. Furthermore, business process guidelines and an e-learning platform will be developed to drive the dissemination and exploitation of the Reincarnate results.

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Fulfilment of Description of Action (DoA) in Deliverable 3.1

Summarised objectives as stated in DoA	Results presented in this deliverable
<p>WP 3 scope and objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - This WP aims at developing solutions and possibilities to adapt buildings and their products to new uses. It also targets the development of new innovative methods to design high-performance materials from recyclables. 	<p>Addressed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In this deliverable a comprehensive decision-making framework is developed that supports asset managers and building owners, in choosing the most appropriate circular adaptive reuse scenario on both the building and component level. - The decision-making framework can be found in section 3. - The architectural concepts in the form of circular adaptive reuse scenarios can be found in section 4.2.1. - The product specific decision-making framework can be found in section 3.4.7.
<p>Task 3.1 scope and objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - This task will suggest architectural concepts for the adaptive reuse of functionally obsolete buildings, incorporating principles of a circular economy. 	<p>Addressed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The architectural concepts take the form of circular adaptive reuse scenario outlined in section 4.2.1. The scenarios combine the future oriented scenario approach with the more practical architectural strategies outlined in section 4.2.1 – step 4G. - The principles of a circular economy take the form of the Circular Building Adaptability strategies outlined by Hamida et al. (2023), which are integrated in the scenarios.

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- Although adaptive reuse itself can be considered as a circular approach, past approaches have not considered the full potential of circular building approaches, by for example considering alternative (off site) re-use purposes of building components as well as re-usability and adaptability of the building after the initial intervention. Thus, as a first step, circular principles will be added to existing concepts for adaptive re-use.
- A decision model will be developed to support the choice between circular adaptive re-use strategies as a second part of the REINCARNATE innovation Circular Decision Making for Real Estate Assets that focuses on understanding renovation and refurbishment possibilities.
- The circular principles in the form of the Circular Building Adaptability strategies are integrated with the adaptive reuse scenarios in section 4.2.1.
- This deliverables considers the full potential of circular building approaches through the use of cross-impact balance analysis for scenario development, in which a full spectrum of potential scenarios are considered (see section 4.2.1.) Besides the future oriented nature of the scenarios more practical circular building approaches are included in the form of the product-level decision-making framework in section 3.4.7.
- The process oriented decision-making framework allows for an iterative cycle in which buildings can go through the decision-model multiples times which makes it possible to derive the most appropriate scenario after the initial intervention.
- The decision model takes the form of the three level decision-making framework which can be used to find 1) the initial intervention direction, 2) the most appropriate circular adaptive reuse scenario and based on this scenario, 3) the most suitable strategy for re-use purposes of building components.
- The decision-making framework shares a lot of overlap with the deliverable 2.2 and together form the innovation: strategic circular decision-making for real estate assets.

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	<p>components in existing buildings, from deliverable 1.3 of the INSITER project, can be used for the condition assessment of the building (1st level decision-model) and building products (3rd level decision-model).</p>
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1. Introduction

The construction sector is approaching a major shift, fueled by the demand for sustainability and advancements in digital technology. In order to advance the construction sector towards a circular industry, circular innovations need to be developed that: increase the utilization of construction and demolition waste, create new value chains and sustainable business models, reduce CO2 emissions, and increase the independence of the EU construction market in the international market for construction products and materials. This report for Deliverable 3.1 in the Reincarnate project introduces a circular decision-making framework for the adaptive refurbishment and renovation of real estate assets.

This report was created in collaboration with the Reincarnate partners: Technical University of Berlin (TUB), Demo Consultants (DMO), and 3L (3L). The collaboration under the Reincarnate umbrella enables the creation of a systematic circular decision-making framework that helps stakeholders of building projects decide on the most appropriate intervention scenario. Deliverables 2.2 and 3.1 together aim to form the innovation: strategic circular decision-making for real estate assets at a Technical Readiness Level (TRL) of 4-6. The deliverables respond to task 2.2 and task 3.1 in the Reincarnate project which have the following objectives: enable asset managers and decision-makers to avoid construction waste in the first place by extending the lifetime of buildings and adapting buildings to new uses, by utilizing the Circular Potential Information Management (CP-IM) platform.

This report includes a comprehensive decision-making framework that combines theoretical knowledge with an implementation example. Three decision-making levels are established, that help asset managers and building owners in the development and the decision between circular adaptive reuse scenarios, on both the building and product levels.

This report outlines the scope and limitations of the research conducted in the current project, which has reached a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of 4-6. At this stage, the methodologies and concepts are mainly theoretical and remain at a conceptual level. Therefore, the results discussed have not yet undergone practical testing. However, future testing is planned in various demo cases, detailed in section 6, which will provide empirical data to validate the findings and methodologies presented in this report.

2. Background and Motivation

2.1. Theoretical background

2.1.1. Environmental impact of buildings

Buildings worldwide are responsible for 39% of the global carbon emissions (WGBC, 2019). With the world's population approaching ten billion people (United Nations, 2022), the global building stock is expected to double in size (WGBC, 2019). This growth will be accompanied by the consumption of vast amounts of natural resources, with an estimated doubling of the total consumption of raw materials by the middle of the century (Pothen, 2017). Carbon emissions are released throughout the building's lifecycle, but emissions in the manufacturing, transportation, construction, and end-of-life phases have been largely overlooked (WGBC, 2019). Commonly referred to as embodied carbon, these emissions contribute to around 11% of all global carbon emissions (WGBC, 2019).

As operational carbon is reduced, embodied carbon will continue to grow in importance as a proportion of total emissions. Besides the consumption of raw materials and the emissions of greenhouse gasses like CO₂, buildings also account for a vast majority of the world's total waste (Sapuyay, 2016). It is estimated that construction and demolition waste (CDW) accounts for 30% of the world's total waste stock, which includes waste generated from construction, renovation, and demolition activities (Purchase et al., 2021). Building demolition waste can have several negative effects on the environment, economy, and society (Lu & Yuan, 2011). Demolition waste often ends up in landfills, taking up valuable space, and contributing to environmental pollution (Menegaki & Damigos, 2018). The waste may also contain hazardous materials, such as asbestos, lead, and mercury, which can leach into the soil and water, posing health risks to nearby communities (Lu & Yuan, 2011). Moreover, the disposal of demolition waste requires energy-intensive processes, contributing to greenhouse gas emissions and climate change (Purchase et al., 2021).

2.1.2. Demolition and functional obsolescence

Most buildings that are demolished have not yet reached the end of their physical use life (Liu et al., 2014). Although the average physical lifespan of buildings is estimated to be around 60-100 years (Faqih et al., 2020), the real average lifetime of a building is estimated to be only around 34 years (Liu et al., 2014). Physical life span refers to the period a building gets demolished because the major components of the building physically reach their life span and are no longer technically useable (Liu et al., 2014). Buildings are however not demolished because they are old or in bad condition, but because developers want to demolish them (Iizuka, 1988).

External factors such as economic, political, and locational aspects of a building are found to be more important in determining its lifespan than internal physical factors (Braid, 2001; Brueckner, 1980). No significant relationship between the structural systems of a building and the actual use life of a building were found (O'Connor, 2004). Market dynamics like city population and housing preferences are however directly linked to building demolition. As a city seeks to house more people, the ground rents rise and landlords or developers replace small buildings with larger ones to get more profit (Hufbauer & Severn, 1974). The most common reason for building demolition is functional obsolescence (Liu et al., 2014). The functional life span refers to the period before which a building loses its functional value due to societal or lifestyle changes (S. Wilkinson, 2014). When buildings become functionally obsolete, they no longer meet the functional requirements that correspond to their intended initial function (Wilkinson, 2014). The functional lifespan of a building can also be exterminated through technological progress (Baum, 1991; Blakstad, 2001). Changes in technology with relation to the layout and facilities offered in new buildings can alter the user requirements, creating the possibility that buildings get functionally outdated already after their first lease period (Wilkinson et al., 2014). A mismatch between the technical and functional lifespan of buildings can therefore lead to structural vacancy which in turn leads to demolition (Remøy, 2010).

2.1.3. Adaptive reuse as a sustainable strategy

To cope with negative externalities from building demolition and to extend the functional lifetime of buildings, adaptive reuse (AR) has become a well-established strategy in the field of architecture and the built environment (Langston et al., 2008). Adaptive reuse is defined as *“the process of extending the useful life of historic, old, obsolete, and derelict buildings, by seeking to maximize the reuse and retention of existing structures and fabrics”* (Shahi et al., 2020). The classic definition focuses on the change in use; a process of converting a building for a new use, different from the initial aim of its construction (Douglas, 2006). Adaptive reuse therefore differs from other building adaptation practices like refurbishment and renovation, where the focus lies on extending the functional lifetime of the building for the same use (Shahi et al., 2020). Adaptive reuse is not a new phenomenon by any means (Lanz & Pendlebury, 2022).

The conversion of buildings from one use to another has taken place at any place, and at all times, internationally, and on different scales (S. J. Wilkinson et al., 2014). Adaptive reuse practices in the past happened simply because demolition and the construction of new buildings needed more time, energy, and money compared to reuse (S. J. Wilkinson et al., 2014). Adaptive reuse as a strategy for a sustainable built environment has gained traction over the years. Adaptive reuse as an alternative to demolition and replacement has many social, environmental, and economic benefits. By adaptively reusing a building embodied energy is preserved (Kumari et al., 2020), and the further use of operational energy is reduced (Langston et al., 2008). Preventing demolition through the reuse of buildings furthermore results in environmental advantages including reducing construction waste, consuming fewer natural resources and raw materials (Conejos, 2013), emitting less greenhouse gases (Yung & Chan, 2012), and controlling urban sprawl (Sanchez et al., 2019). Other social advantages of adaptive reuse include improved safety, quality of living, occupant health, and help restore and maintain the identity of a building (Aigwi et al., 2018; Shen & Langston, 2010). When it comes to economic advantages, adaptive reuse leads to an increase in the property value of the building and other surrounding buildings (Sanchez et al., 2019), and the generation of jobs on the site and in its vicinity (Chan et al., 2015).

2.1.4. Challenges of adaptive reuse

Although adaptive reuse is accompanied by many benefits, it also faces many challenges and uncertainties. Adaptive reuse has a higher risk of return on investment compared to new construction which can scare away owners and investors (Shiple et al., 2006). There is also an increased probability of cost and time overruns in adaptive reuse projects because most building conversion projects deal with vacant and old buildings susceptible to unknown conditions (Bullen, 2007). Latent defects, contamination, hazardous materials, and structural defects are all factors that can increase the cost and duration of adaptive reuse projects (Bullen, 2007). Another important factor that is often overlooked is that the environmental benefits accompanied by adaptive reuse are not guaranteed. An example of this is that the reuse of existing buildings may not completely reduce the need and desire for new construction. Known as a spill-over effect, the adaptive reuse of a building may result in more buildings being built overall rather than less (Cooper & Gutowski, 2017). Another overlooked aspect is that an adaptively reused building could fall short of today's expected standards (Bullen & Love, 2011).

The main problem of adaptive reuse projects according to *Mısırlısoy & Günce* is concerned with the random decision of the new function without in-depth analysis, due to the lack of a clear methodology for the adaptive reuse decision-making process (Mısırlısoy & Günçe, 2016). The decision on whether and how to reuse a building entails a complex set of considerations, including location, heritage importance, architectural assets, market trends, quality of the environment, people's needs, and physical site conditions (Bullen & Love, 2011). Many researchers agree that the decision-making to adaptive reuse of existing buildings is a complex matter, due to the many stakeholders, and decision criteria involved (Bullen & Love, 2011; Douglas, 2006; S. Wilkinson et al., 2009). There is however no clear consensus on the decision criteria and the decision support tool when it comes to adaptive reuse (Arfa et al., 2022; Mısırlısoy & Günçe, 2016; Unver et al., 2022).

2.2. Problem statement

The adaptive reuse of buildings is considered a good strategy for reducing the environmental impacts of buildings while preserving the cultural and historic significance (Langston et al., 2008). Finding a new use for the building is a difficult problem in the decision-making process since it includes many decision criteria and stakeholders (Bullen & Love, 2011; Douglas, 2006; S. Wilkinson et al., 2009). A lack of guidance is often mentioned as a common barrier in the adaptive reuse process (Pintossi et al., 2021), and there also seems to be a lack of agreement in the scientific community to achieve a more uniform vision surrounding the decision criteria for adaptive reuse (Bosone et al., 2021).

Multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) models have become increasingly popular in helping decision-makers make informed decisions, by providing a structured approach to assess and compare alternative solutions for adaptive reuse (Nadkarni & Puthuvayi, 2020). Determining the alternatives for the new use is an important aspect in decision-making for adaptive reuse, but most alternatives used in prior studies have either been really broad (functional use) (Haroun et al., 2019), or really specific (pre-defined design options) (Vizzarri et al., 2021). A general overview of what is possible when pursuing adaptive reuse in the form of holistic typologies for adaptive reuse scenarios is currently missing (van Laar et al., 2024). Most current decision models on adaptive reuse also do not consider circularity strategies beyond reusing the building itself (Foster & Kreinin, 2020). Tools to assess the impacts and orient adaptive reuse interventions from the perspective of the circular economy are lacking (Bosone et al., 2021). Therefore the main objective of this deliverable is to develop: a holistic decision-making tool that incorporates appropriate decision criteria for adaptive reuse, and circular adaptive reuse scenarios, that could help decision-makers in choosing the best circular adaptive reuse strategies for functionally obsolete buildings.

3. Proposed decision-making framework for adaptive refurbishment and renovation of real estate assets

3.1. Aim and objective of the decision-making framework

The objective of the decision-making framework for the adaptive refurbishment and renovation of real estate assets is to give asset managers and building owners potential architectural concepts for the adaptive reuse of buildings, through the use of circular adaptive reuse strategies. By developing a decision-making framework that systemizes the development and the decision between circular adaptive reuse scenarios, stakeholders of adaptive reuse projects can explore adaptive reuse and renovation possibilities on three different decision-making levels: 1st level decision framework in which the initial intervention direction is established, the 2nd level decision-making framework in which circular adaptive reuse scenarios are developed and decided upon, and a 3rd level decision-making framework in which the most appropriate End-of-Life (EoL) strategy can be chosen for building products.

The starting point for using the decision-making framework is a functionally obsolete building that does not meet the current requirements of the stakeholders. An intervention is therefore necessary. However, what intervention should be chosen (renovation, adaptive reuse, deconstruction, etc.), How this intervention should take place (what scenario is most appropriate), and how this intervention can happen in a circular fashion, often remain unclear. The aim of this report is therefore to support asset managers and building owners in answering these questions by offering a stepwise decision-making process guideline.

3.1.1. Stepwise decision-making process guideline

The proposed stepwise structure for the Reincarnate decision-making framework for the adaptive refurbishment of real estate assets is presented in Figure 1. The approach comprises of 7 steps divided over 3 levels of decision-making frameworks. The three levels of the framework are described in short here. A more elaborate explanation of the three levels can be found in section: 3.2, 3.3, 3.4 and 3.5. The decision-making framework presented in this deliverable shares a lot of similarities with the decision-making framework for deliverable 2.2: *Circular decision-making for extending the use life of real estate assets*¹, as they both correspond to the same innovation: 7. *Strategic circular decision-making for real estate assets*. Some parts of the framework are more elaborately explained deliverable 2.2.

¹ <https://www.reincarnate-project.eu/innovations/>

1st-level decision-making framework – first intervention direction

In the first level, the building is assessed on its current: condition, utilization, and potential reward of the building. Based on this, a first intervention direction can be chosen: The first-level decision-making framework is the same for deliverables 2.2 and 3.1 and guides stakeholders towards either the adaptive reuse decision-making framework, the renovation decision-making framework, or the product-level decision-making framework, based on the characteristics of the current building.

2nd level decision-making framework(s) – circular adaptive reuse scenarios

Once a first intervention direction is chosen based on the outcomes of the 1st level decision-making framework, either the renovation decision-making framework (deliverable 2.2) or the adaptive reuse decision-making framework (deliverable 3.1) comes into play. Stakeholders first choose the objectives and criteria they find important for their future project. Then, based on the objectives, stakeholders can choose to develop their own scenarios or choose the default scenarios. Lastly, stakeholders quantify their preferences and a final performance ranking of the scenarios can be made.

3rd level decision-making framework – product-level decision-making

The third level decision-making framework is concerned with determining the next life of building products. Based on the chosen scenario in step 2, requirements can be set up that determine what products remain in the building and what products need a new life. The new life of building products can then be determined based on the product-level decision-making framework in: (section 3.4.7). This framework can also be used separately from the other levels. A detailed outline of the 3rd level decision-making framework can be found in deliverable 2.2².

² <https://www.reincarnate-project.eu/>

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Figure 1: Proposed decision-making framework for the adaptive refurbishment and renovation of real estate assets (by author)

3.2. 1st level decision-making framework

3.2.1. Current building assessment

Before we can decide on the most appropriate intervention for a building, it is important to understand its current condition. Mapping the current condition and utilization of a building before deciding on an intervention is crucial for several reasons. First, it provides a comprehensive understanding of the building's physical state, identifying issues such as structural weaknesses, energy inefficiencies, or outdated systems that need addressing. This assessment ensures that interventions are not just cosmetic but address underlying problems, enhancing the building's longevity and functionality. Secondly, understanding how the building is currently used helps to tailor interventions to meet the actual needs of its (future) occupants. It allows for the optimization of space, improvement of comfort and safety, and enhancement of energy and resource efficiency based on current and future usage patterns. Lastly, this initial mapping forms a baseline against which the success and impact of interventions can be measured. It ensures that investments are directed where they are most needed and are likely to have the greatest positive effect, thereby ensuring cost-effectiveness and satisfaction among stakeholders. Without this foundational knowledge, interventions risk being misaligned with the building's needs, potentially leading to wasted resources and opportunities for improvement.

Figure 2: 1st level decision-making framework (by author)

3.2.2. Adapted IconCUR model

For the initial 1st level decision between different intervention options, the IconCUR model developed by Langston & Smith (2012), was adapted for our decision-making framework. The IconCUR model is a conceptual framework designed for making better decisions regarding the management of built facilities, especially at an early stage in the decision-making process (Langston & Smith, 2012). It incorporates a weighted matrix methodology to assess the performance of built assets based on three main factors: condition, utilization, and reward. These factors are evaluated to produce performance scores, which are then used to map potential property management decisions in a three-dimensional space over time. The model's application facilitates a practical approach to decision-making using an adaptive management philosophy, enabling property managers to quickly assess, identify, and rank opportunities based on the potential value they add. This is achieved through the model's ability to present decisions spatially, allowing for objective measurement of the distance between current property performance and the optimal decision corners that define the cubic boundaries of the model. The IconCUR model exemplifies a useful tool in property management by emphasizing the quick assessment and ranking of property management decisions, highlighting its practicality and adaptability in a real-world setting (Langston & Smith, 2012). In this deliverable, the IconCUR model is simplified (see section 2.2.4, and Figure 8), to make it suitable to serve as the 1st level decision-making framework.

Figure 3: The IconCUR conceptual framework for building intervention decisions (Langston & Smith, 2012)

3.2.3. Step 1: Map the current condition, utilization, and potential reward of the building

The first step in the decision-making framework is to assess the current building on *condition*, *utilization*, and potential *reward*. This is done with the adapted IconCUR assessment worksheet (figure 26). In this worksheet four main criteria can be measured, using a weighted matrix method. In the assessment sheet, each criterion is laid out in columns with key sub-criteria, each assigned a weight reflecting its importance. Correspondingly, key elements are listed in rows under each criterion, also weighted based on their impact. For the weighing of sub-criteria and elements, a simple weighting percentage method can be used following the formula in which: W_i is the percentage weight of the i -th criterion, w_i is the raw weight assigned to i -th the criterion based on its perceived importance, n is the total number of criteria, and $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j$ is the sum of all raw weights assigned.

$$W_i = \frac{w_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n w_j} \times 100\%$$

(1)

Performance at the intersection of each criterion and element is then assessed through the use of key questions on a five-point Likert scale (5 = strongly agree, 4 = agree, 3 = neutral, 2 = disagree, 1 = strongly disagree, 0 = not applicable). The assessment worksheet can be found in the appendix (Appendix 1). The weighting and performance rating of the criteria and elements can be either done separately by each stakeholder and combined together, or done together in a workshop setting. A combined (weighted) score for each criterion or sub-criterion can then be calculated, which is used for placing the building on the 1st level decision-making matrix.

The assessment of the condition and utilization of the building is done in this framework using the original criteria of the IconCUR model. However, the 1st level of decision-making assessment can be adapted based on the requirements of a specific region. The evaluation of the initial intervention direction is based on a 2D matrix consisting of condition on the x-axis and utilization on the y-axis. The logic behind the matrix is not dependent on the exact assessment method for the condition and utilization and can be replaced by regulatory standards related to a specific region, such as the Dutch NEN276724³.

³. <https://www.nen.nl/bouw/beheer-en-onderhoud/conditiemeting>

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Condition

The term '*condition*' refers to the physical characteristics of a building, which is categorized by three sub-criteria: design standard, maintained service level, and regulatory compliance. '*Design standard*' concerns the quality of construction, touching on aspects like durability and aesthetics. '*Maintained service level*' involves the property's upkeep, covering regular maintenance and cleaning. '*Regulatory compliance*' deals with adherence to laws, focusing on areas like certification and safety measures. For the criteria *condition*, five building elements are distinguished on which the sub-criteria are rated: structure (foundations and superstructure), exterior envelope (façade and roof), interior finishes/fitout (subdivision, finishes, equipment, and furnishings), engineering systems (mechanical, electrical, and hydraulic services), and external works (site works and external services). The weighting of the elements can be based on the proportional construction cost of each element (Langston & Smith, 2012).

CONDITION	3.55				(high)
		design standard	maintained service level	regulatory compliance	
	weighting	50%	25%	25%	100%
structure	20%	4	4	4	4.00
exterior envelope	30%	4	4	4	4.00
interior finishes/fitout	20%	3	3	4	3.25
engineering services	20%	2	3	3	2.50
external works	10%	4	3	5	4.00
	100%	3.40	3.50	3.90	

Figure 4: An example evaluation of the criteria '*condition*' in the IconCUR model (Langston & Smith, 2012)

Utilization

The criterion '*utilization*' reflects the occupancy characteristics of a property and is assessed through three sub-criteria: *demand or relevance*, *fitness for purpose*, and *user satisfaction*. '*Demand or relevance*' evaluates the property's level of use, including factors like occupancy rates and demand for the function. '*Fitness for purpose*' measures how well the property's design meets its functional goals, considering aspects such as flexibility and technological support. '*User satisfaction*' gauges how well the property is received by its users, with considerations like comfort and perceived utility. The following elements can be distinguished for utilization: internal space (the fully enclosed area, excluding primary functional and service spaces), external space (covered, unenclosed areas), outdoor site area (land excluding the building's footprint), equipment and fitout (main functional spaces), and engineering systems (service areas). The weighting of the elements can be based on the relative magnitude of the different zones (Langston & Smith, 2012).

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UTILIZATION	0.96	demand or relevance	fitness for purpose	user satisfaction	(very low)
internal space (feca)	30%	1	2	2	1.60
external space (uca)	10%	0	2	0	0.80
outdoor site area	10%	0	0	0	0.00
equipment and fitout	30%	1	1	0	0.80
engineering systems	20%	1	1	0	0.80
	100%	0.80	1.30	0.60	

Figure 5: An example evaluation of the criteria 'utilization' in the IconCUR model (Langston & Smith, 2012)

Reward

Reward is based on the collective utility that is received from the building. It is defined as the net benefit for all stakeholders in terms of financial social and environmental benefits. If the benefits coming from the current building are already high, then there is little opportunity for improvement through intervention. If the net benefits are low, then an intervention can significantly improve the collective utility (Langston & Smith, 2012). The criterion reward is also dependent on the interest of stakeholders. Not all stakeholders have the same interest in the project and therefore this can impact the collective utility. The criterion 'reward' is calculated as the score for collective utility multiplied by the score for stakeholder interest and divided by the number of stakeholders (in this case 5).

$$R_i = \frac{CU_i \times SI_i}{5}$$

(2)

If all stakeholders have excellent interest in the short, medium, and long term, then reward would equal collective utility. The sub-criteria and elements of collective utility and stakeholder interest are explained below:

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Collective utility

The criterion: *collective utility*, is measured through three sub-criteria: *economic performance*, *culture and heritage*, and *environmental values*. 'Economic performance' addresses the financial benefits generated by the property, including aspects like return on investment and financial risk. 'Culture and heritage' focuses on the social contributions of the property, encompassing factors such as community enhancement and the creation of a sense of place. 'Environmental values' examine the sustainability impacts of the property, including its carbon footprint and efforts in habitat protection. These sub-criteria are measured according to the following elements: operational viability (ongoing feasibility), locational context (accessibility to markets), risk and opportunity (preparation for future changes), asset valuation (potential for investment appreciation), and profile/mission (enhancement of reputation). The importance of these goals in relation to the overall success of the project can guide the allocation of weights to each element (Langston & Smith, 2012).

COLLECTIVE UTILITY	3.00				(high)
	weighting	economic performance 20%	culture and heritage 40%	environmental values 40%	100%
operational viability	30%	2	2	3	2.40
locational context	20%	5	5	1	3.40
risk and opportunity	20%	2	4	3	3.20
asset valuation	20%	3	5	1	3.00
profile/mission	10%	4	5	2	3.60
	100%	3.00	3.90	2.10	

Figure 6: An example evaluation of the criteria 'collective utility' in the IconCUR model (Langston & Smith, 2012)

Stakeholder interest

The criterion: *stakeholder interest*, is defined by the level of engagement stakeholders have with the outcomes provided by the property. This engagement is measured across three time perspectives: *short-term*, *medium-term*, and *long-term*. The short-term perspective covers benefits that occur within the first five years. The medium-term perspective spans benefits accruing in the following fifteen years, while the long-term perspective considers benefits that occur throughout the remainder of the property's useful life. For the measurement of stakeholder interest, the following 5 elements (stakeholders) are distinguished: the building owner (controlling organization), building user (employees and customers), facility manager (custodian or site manager), sponsor/financier (government authority or private

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investor/banker), and the community (general public). The weighting of each element is determined by the stakeholders' relative influence and control, with considerations given to factors of power, legitimacy, and urgency (Langston & Smith, 2012).

STAKEHOLDER INTEREST	3.80				(high)
	weighting	short-term perspective 50%	medium-term perspective 25%	long-term perspective 25%	100%
building owner	40%	3	4	5	4.20
building user	20%	3	2	1	1.80
facility manager	10%	5	5	5	5.00
sponsor/financier	10%	5	3	1	2.60
community	20%	5	5	5	5.00
	100%	3.80	3.80	3.80	

Figure 7: An example evaluation of the criteria 'stakeholder interest' in the IconCUR model (Langston & Smith, 2012)

3.2.4. Step 2: Decide on the first intervention direction based on the 1st level decision-making framework

Step 2 in the decision-making framework is concerned with the decision for the best intervention strategy based on the current building. In the original IconCUR model, 9 intervention options are distinguished. However, for this decision-making framework, only the four corner options are included: Deconstruct, Adaptive Reuse, Renovation, and Retain. Based on the current condition and utilization of the building, the project is placed on the 1st level decision-making matrix (figure 9). The scale for all axes is categorized as follows: 0–1 (very low), 1–2 (low), 2–3 (moderate), 3–4 (high), and 4–5 (very high). The positioning of a building within the matrix can be used to assess and rank properties in a portfolio based on their spatial coordinates relative to corners. For instance, buildings that are horizontally closer to the adaptive reuse edge indicate a higher certainty in the decision to undertake this type of intervention. Implementing such a decision would shift the property's position in the matrix, ideally improving the value associated with all three coordinates (Langston & Smith, 2012). The more significant the shift from old to new coordinates, the more impactful the decision is considered, and if the values increase, the higher the anticipated success. An effective decision would result in the property's coordinates moving closer to the retain/extend corner post-intervention, symbolizing a high reward. The four intervention options are explained below.

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Figure 8: The 1st level decision-making matrix, adapted from the IconCUR model by (Langston & Smith, 2012) (by author)

Retain

If both the condition and the utilization of the building receive high scores (3-5), then the building ends up in the top right corner. This means that there is a demand for the building in its current use, the building is fit for its current purpose and the user satisfaction is high. The building also scores high for condition meaning that the design standard is high, the building is well maintained and the building conditions comply with regulations. When the project is situated in this corner there is no reason to physically intervene in the building and the building should be retained. Although no physical interventions are necessary there are still some operational strategies, in terms of circular building adaptability that could be applied to the building which are outlined in Hamida et al. (2023).

Deconstruct

If both the condition and utilization of the building score low, then the building is placed in the lower left-hand corner (deconstruct). This means that there is no demand for the building, the building is not fit for purpose, and the building does not comply with maintenance and regulatory standards. In other words: the building cannot function anymore as a building and needs to be deconstructed. However, because the building still contains valuable materials and products, the product-level decision-making model (section 3.4.7) should be visited. This product-level decision-making framework assesses building products on their circularity potential and helps determine a new use for these products. If the building is situated in this corner the stakeholders move from the 1st level decision-making framework directly to the 3rd level decision-making framework, bypassing the 2nd level decision-making framework, as the building will not be used as a building anymore. A detailed description of the 3rd level decision-making framework can be found in deliverable 2.2: *Circular decision-making for extending the use life of real estate assets* ⁴.

Renovation

When the building scores (relatively) high on building utilization and low on building condition then it ends up in the top left-hand corner (Renovation). This means that the building is fit for its original function, there is demand for this function and the users are (relatively) satisfied with the building. However, the condition of the building needs an upgrade. This can have several reasons like the building systems being outdated, the maintenance of the building being inadequate, or the building does not meet regulatory standards or user needs. To determine the best renovation scenario in this case the 2nd level decision-making framework for renovation should be used. This framework can be found in deliverable 2.2: *Circular decision-making for extending the use life of real estate assets*.

Adaptive Reuse

When the condition of the building scores (relatively) high but the utilization scores (relatively) low, the building ends up in the bottom right-hand corner (Adaptive Reuse). In this case, the physical condition of the building is still good, but the building is either not fit for its original function, there is no demand for the current function, or the user satisfaction is low. This means that changing the function of the building could increase the utilization, and the building can be adaptively reused. After adaptive reuse is determined as the best option following the 1st level

⁴ [Link to deliverable 2.2](#)

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decision-making framework, the 2nd level decision-making framework can be used to determine the most suitable adaptive reuse scenario (see section 3.4).

1st level decision-making framework – decision analysis

After the building is assessed based on the current condition and utilization, an intervention decision can be made based on the 1st level decision-making matrix. Although the matrix is represented as a 2D model, the 3rd dimension (reward) is used in this framework as a form of validation. ‘*Reward*’ measures the potential value added after the intervention. If the reward score is high this means that there is little opportunity for improvement and also little value added. In this case, another intervention could be considered. If the reward score is low, this means that there is a lot of room for improvement, and going for this intervention therefore adds a lot of value. When a building falls well within one of the quadrants (close to the corner), and the reward value is relatively low, then this intervention option is generally considered the right decision (Langston & Smith, 2012). The closer the building is located to one of the corners in the matrix, the higher the level of certainty attached to this intervention decision.

The 1st level decision-making framework is a conceptual model that can help practitioners in deciding on the most appropriate intervention direction. However, it is crucial to remember that such models are guides rather than prescriptive solutions. Stakeholders are not obligated to strictly follow the outcomes suggested by the decision model. This model is designed to assist stakeholders in finding the best intervention direction based on their input.

3.3. 2nd level decision-making framework

After the decision for adaptive reuse has been made following the 1st level decision-making framework, the 2nd level decision-making framework comes into play. The 2nd level in the decision-making framework is concerned with the decision of what specific scenario is most appropriate to the wants and needs of the stakeholders. This level is concerned with the future objectives and requirements set by the stakeholders and is more future-oriented, compared to the 1st level in which the building is assessed on the current condition and utilization.

Figure 9: The stepwise approach to the 2nd level decision-making framework and scenario development process (by author)

For the 2nd level decision-making framework, the approach of multicriteria decision-making is used. Although many different multicriteria decision-making methods exist, common steps can be distinguished, that need to be taken to arrive at a final decision. Key steps involved in a typical MCDM framework and how they contribute to effective decision-making are explained in the next section.

Step 3: Define the problem, objectives, and criteria

The initial phase of an MCDM framework involves clearly articulating the problem at hand. This entails identifying the decision objectives and criteria. Decision objectives encapsulate the overarching goals and aspirations, while criteria represent the factors influencing the decision. In (section 3.3.1) a pool of criteria and objectives are identified following an integrative literature review (van Laar et al., 2024). Based on the preferences of the stakeholders objectives can be chosen from this pool for the inclusion in the MCDM framework and for the development of scenarios.

Step 4: Develop adaptive reuse scenarios OR choose the default adaptive reuse scenarios

In MCDM, alternatives refer to the different options or scenarios that are being evaluated against a set of criteria or objectives. These alternatives are essentially the potential choices available to decision-makers, each with its unique set of features and outcomes. In this framework, alternatives take the form of scenarios. Stakeholders can opt to develop their own scenarios following the approach outlined in (section 3.4.4) or choose the default scenarios developed in (section 4.2.1). The scenarios developed for this decision-making framework serve two purposes: as outcomes of the multi-criteria decision-making model, and as imaginative future end-states to show stakeholders what is possible when pursuing adaptive reuse.

Step 5: Quantify the criteria and objectives based on the preferences of the stakeholders

In a multicriteria decision-making framework, quantifying criteria and preferences is essential. This step involves the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) to weigh objectives chosen in step 1 through pairwise comparisons. The stakeholders assess the relative importance of each objective, compute weights, and check for consistency. A consistency ratio above 0.1 indicates potential contradictions in judgments, suggesting a need for revisions. This process ensures that the decision-making reflects stakeholder priorities accurately and logically.

Step 6: Decide on the most appropriate circular adaptive reuse scenario

After capturing the stakeholders' preferences, including the objectives and their associated weights, the next step is to evaluate the adaptive reuse scenarios according to these preferences. The final stage of the multicriteria decision-making framework focuses on decision analysis. In this phase, the performance of each scenario is assessed against the set objectives and combined with the weights determined earlier to calculate a comprehensive global performance score for each option. The ranking of the scenarios is done according to the Fuzzy-TOPSIS method (Dymova et al., 2013). This score helps in ranking the scenarios, thereby simplifying the decision-making process.

3.3.1. Step 3: Define the problem, objectives, and criteria

Criteria and objectives are essential in a multicriteria decision-making framework as they provide a structured approach for considering all relevant factors and align stakeholders towards common goals, ensuring informed and effective decision outcomes (Cinelli et al., 2020). Although publications on decision-making criteria and objectives in adaptive reuse exist, many have focussed on specific decisions within a distinct phase, and few have considered the process as a whole (van Laar et al., 2024). Because the proposed decision-making framework for the adaptive refurbishment of real estate assets consists of multiple decision stages, with specific decisions being made at each stage, the criteria and objectives need to align with these stages (van Laar et al., 2024).

To identify relevant objectives and criteria for the multi-criteria decision-making framework, an integrative literature review was undertaken that investigated the decision criteria in each stage. Through this integrative literature review with a systematic search strategy, three phases in the adaptive reuse decision-making process were substantiated: pre-project phase, preparation phase, and post-completion phase, and for each phase relevant criteria and objectives were identified (van Laar et al., 2024). In the pre-project phase, the decision focuses on preserving reusing, or demolishing a building. The decision to adaptively reuse the buildings has not yet been made and the phase is characterized by defining the scope of the project, as well as mapping the potential for adaptation and adaptive reuse. In the preparation phase, the decision to adaptively reuse the buildings has been made, and decision criteria are used to compare different options and decide on the best new use or design alternative. These alternatives can take shape in various ways. The post-completion phase roughly consists of three parts: 1) assessing the building on future adaptive reuse potential based on adaptive reuse

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projects, 2) success evaluation/ assessment of the adaptive reuse project, and 3) determining whether or not the new use is appropriate (van Laar et al., 2024).

Figure 10: Different phases of the adaptive reuse process (van Laar et al., 2024)

Because for the 2nd level decision-making framework, the decision for adaptive reuse has been made following the outcomes of the 1st level decision-making framework, the objectives and criteria identified in the preparation phase are most relevant. In this phase, the decision to adaptively reuse the buildings has been made, and decision criteria are used to compare different alternatives. For the preparation phase, 64 criteria divided over 24 objectives were identified. Table 1 presents the proposed pool of all objectives and criteria that can be used to develop circular adaptive reuse scenarios (section 3.4.4) and to assess the adaptive reuse projects. The inclusion of criteria and objectives in the multicriteria decision-making framework is based on the preferences of the stakeholders, and can also be combined or altered when developing the scenarios (see section 4.2.1).

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Table 1: Objectives and criteria in the preparation phase (van Laar et al., 2024)

Politics and Regulations	To increase political support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (local) political support
	To successfully manage the adaptive reuse process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ownership Time management
Economic	To comply with urban master plans and zoning regulations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Urban master plan Zoning policies
	To comply with heritage regulations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Compliance with heritage guidelines
	To comply with the local building codes and regulations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Occupational health and safety Fire safety Standard of finish / design regulations
	To have a positive impact on the local economy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Job creation Economic growth
	To minimize financial risk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Source of finance Initial investment
Socio-Cultural	To increase market potential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Market opportunity due to location
	To reduce costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adaptation / conversion costs Maintenance costs Investment cost Operational costs
	To increase economic returns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increase in market value
	To increase social impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social interaction / social cohesion
Technological	To preserve the historical image of the building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cultural value Aesthetic quality Historical value
	To retain a sense of place / identity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sense of place
	To improve public amenities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public amenities
Environmental	To increase knowledge and expertise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feedback on building performance and use Staff expertise
	To improve building services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Building orientation and solar access glazing and shading Insulation and acoustics Security systems HVAC Energy system GHG emissions Energy consumption Water consumption
Architectural / Physical	To reduce the environmental impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> waste Pollution
	To reduce waste and pollution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Air quality Thermal comfort Acoustics Visual comfort (lighting)
	To safeguard the indoor environmental quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental impact of materials
	To reduce material consumption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Structural integrity
Functional	To safeguard the structural integrity of the building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Building age Building size Building shape
	The physical character of the building allows for adaptive reuse	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Material durability
	To improve the durability of the materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quality of the design
	To preserve the aesthetic quality of the building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Structural grid location Site layout
	The location and site of the building allow for adaptive reuse	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vehicle accessibility Pedestrian accessibility Public transport accessibility Disability accessibility
Functional	To improve the accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Flexibility of spaces / layout Flexibility of service ducts and corridors
	To improve the flexibility and adaptability of the building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Disassembly potential
	To improve the disassembly potential of the building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Spatial flow and atria Building compatibility for new use
Functional	To safeguard the suitability of the building for a new use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Spatial flow and atria Building compatibility for new use

3.4. 2nd Level decision-making framework

3.4.1. The need for circular building adaptive reuse scenarios

In most multi-criteria decision-making models for adaptive reuse, the alternatives that are assessed and compared are either really general, only looking at functional use, or really specific, looking at detailed design options (van Laar et al., 2024). In the decision-making process of adaptive reuse, there is however a need for a more general overview of options that give decision-makers a glance into what is possible when pursuing adaptive reuse (van Laar et al., 2024). Circularity strategies beyond reusing the building itself are also lacking in current adaptive reuse projects (Foster & Kreinin, 2020), highlighting the need for more holistic intervention scenarios for adaptive reuse that incorporate circular (design) strategies.

3.4.2. Why scenarios?

Scenarios are a valuable input for multi-criteria decision-making in the context of adaptive reuse decision-making because they facilitate comprehensive, future-oriented insights that are essential for evaluating long-term sustainability and functionality (Bottero et al., 2022). Adaptive reuse, which involves repurposing buildings for new uses, is inherently complex, as it requires balancing historical preservation with modern needs (S. J. Wilkinson et al., 2014). By incorporating scenarios, decision-makers can systematically explore various future states and potential changes in environmental, social, and economic conditions. This foresight enables stakeholders to assess how different reuse options might perform under multiple future uncertainties, ensuring that decisions are robust and flexible (Weimer-Jehle, 2023). Scenarios help in understanding the implications of each choice, not just in the present but over the lifespan of the building, thereby supporting more sustainable and informed decision-making processes. This is crucial for adaptive reuse projects where outcomes must be resilient to future changes and aligned with long-term community and environmental goals.

3.4.3. Scenarios

Scenarios in decision-making typically fall into three broad types: exploratory, predictive, and normative (van Notten et al., 2003). Exploratory scenarios outline a range of possible futures based on varying assumptions about key factors such as technological advances and regulatory changes, helping stakeholders visualize potential outcomes (van Notten et al., 2003). Predictive scenarios, on the other hand, are often used to forecast the most likely future based on current trends and data extrapolation, providing a probabilistic outlook of what might occur (van Notten et al., 2003). Normative scenarios differ fundamentally as they are prescriptive, outlining pathways to achieve desired outcomes or specific strategic goals rather than merely reacting to external changes (van Notten et al., 2003). This forward-thinking approach is particularly advantageous for multicriteria decision-making in areas like adaptive reuse, where the goal is to not only select feasible options but also align decisions with broader sustainability objectives or community values. By focusing on desired end states, normative scenarios enable planners and decision-makers to define clear criteria and evaluate how different decisions contribute to achieving these strategic targets, making them an excellent fit for the structured, goal-oriented nature of MCDM. (McGowan et al., 2019)

Figure 11: Different types of scenarios in scenario research (McGowan et al., 2019)

3.4.4. Step 4: Develop adaptive reuse scenarios OR choose the default adaptive reuse scenarios

For the development of scenarios in this multi-criteria decision-making framework, the cross-impact balance analysis is used. Cross-Impact Balance (CIB) analysis is an analytical method used in the field of futures studies and scenario development. It evaluates how various events, decisions, or trends can influence each other within a given system (Weimer-Jehle, 2023). This method is particularly used for constructing robust and coherent scenarios by systematically assessing the mutual impacts of different elements, such as economic conditions, technological changes, or policy shifts (Weimer-Jehle, 2023). CIB is especially effective for developing normative scenarios, which are scenarios that reflect desired or targeted futures, rather than simply extrapolating from current trends. The strength of CIB in this context lies in its ability to ensure internal consistency among the elements of a scenario (Weimer-Jehle, 2023). It helps in aligning the scenario's components towards a common end state, thus providing strategic guidance on how to achieve specific future goals.

For the development of the scenarios through the CIB method the following approach can be used:

- Step 4A: Selecting scenario descriptors
- Step 4B: Developing future directions
- Step 4C: Identifying relationships
- Step 4D: Constructing scenarios
- Step 4E: Generating consistent scenarios
- Step 4F: Adding visual and narrative elements
- Step 4G: Connecting the scenarios to circular building adaptability strategies

Figure 12: The scenario development process (by author)

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Figure 13: Visualisation of the scenario development process (by author)

Step 4A: Selecting scenario descriptors

The first step in the scenario development process is the selection of the descriptors. Descriptors are central themes used to develop scenarios in an analysis. They help us describe the system we are studying and its key interactions (Weimer-Jehle, 2023). To effectively identify the necessary descriptors, it can be useful to take on a hypothetical future perspective: Imagine you have reached the target year of your scenario analysis and are now tasked with the role of a historian who must describe and explain the developments that have occurred as if they were the past. Consider which topics would be critical to highlight. For this, it is not necessary to dive into every detail but the descriptors need to describe the overall developments in a comprehensible manner.

As a starting point for choosing the scenario descriptors the criteria and objectives identified in the literature review (table 1) can be used as a starting point. Because CIB analyses are typically performed at a high aggregation level (Weimer-Jehle, 2023), given the constrained number of descriptors, criteria, and objectives can be combined into one comprehensive descriptor (see figure 15). This means that a descriptor like: 'Market potential', is concerned with the overall market potential, taking into account different criteria like location, target users, economic return, etc. Collectively, the descriptors should provide meaningful insights about the subject of the scenario analysis (Weimer-Jehle, 2023). Although the number of descriptors is not strictly described there is always a trade-off between adequacy and completeness, and therefore a descriptor field of between 9 and 15 descriptors is recommended (Weimer-Jehle, 2023).

Figure 14: Outline of a descriptor (by author)

Step 4B: Developing future directions

The reason behind doing scenario analysis is that the future is uncertain. The concept of the future's openness is essential in scenario analysis, suggesting that descriptors can evolve in various ways. If the future outcomes of all descriptors were predictable, the system itself would be predictable, eliminating the need for multiple scenarios. In CIB analysis, this openness is addressed by assigning multiple potential outcomes to each descriptor, known as "descriptor variants". These variants outline a spectrum of plausible future directions for each descriptor (Weimer-Jehle, 2023).

These variants need to be both: 'mutually exclusive' and 'collectively exhaustive' to ensure the integrity of the scenario analysis. Mutually exclusive variants mean that each variant is clearly distinct from the others; no two variants should overlap in their definition or implications, thereby avoiding any ambiguity in scenario outcomes (Weimer-Jehle, 2023). Collectively exhaustive, on the other hand, ensures that the variants cover all possible developments for a descriptor, leaving no significant potential outcomes unaddressed (Weimer-Jehle, 2023). This completeness is vital for capturing the full spectrum of future uncertainties and interactions among variables. Typically, each descriptor has two to four variants (Weimer-Jehle, 2023). For the scenario development, ordinal variants should be chosen that have a natural order, which makes it easier to include them in the multicriteria decision-making model. Three variants can be distinguished: a strong variant in which the objective is reached, a medium variant in which the objective is partially reached, and a weak variant in which the objective is not reached.

Figure 15: Outline of descriptors and descriptor variants (by author)

Step 4C: Identifying relationships

After the descriptors and variants are identified the next step in the process is to find credible scenarios in every combination of descriptor variants. Blindly combining each combination of descriptor and variant would result in 14.4 million possible scenarios! This would imply however that all the descriptors are completely independent of each other. It is however unrealistic to think that a descriptor like: “Cost” is not influenced by descriptors like: “*Building Technology*” or “*Building characteristics*”. Simply mixing descriptor variants without considering their interrelationships risks losing the crucial elements that define a good scenario: internal logic and consistency (Weimer-Jehle, 2023). To develop believable scenarios, it is essential to explore these interdependencies.

To identify interdependencies between descriptors “*cross-impacts*” between descriptor variants need to be identified. For all descriptor variants the influence that the development of one descriptor exerts on the development of another descriptor, needs to be assessed based on a seven-point cross-impact rating scale (figure 17) The cross-impact $x \rightarrow y$ answers the question: “*If variant x were to occur for descriptor X, would this promote or hinder variant y for descriptor Y?*”

Figure 16: Example of the identification of relationships in the cross-impact balance analysis

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All cross-impact assessments taken together then form the cross-impact matrix that is used for generating consistent scenarios in step 4D. Filling out the cross-impact balance matrix can be done in a workshop with stakeholders, or through independent interviews, and later combining different matrices together (Weimer-Jehle, 2023).

Step 4D: Constructing scenarios

If the interdependencies among descriptors are not taken into account, any mix of descriptor variants might be seen as a scenario. However, by utilizing the cross-impact matrix, it becomes feasible to evaluate each scenario to determine if it aligns with the interdependencies specified in the matrix, or if contradictions—meaning inconsistencies—emerge. The impact diagram allows us to assess the consistency of each descriptor variant and the scenario as a whole. Figure 18 shows us an impact diagram of one hypothetical scenario (Weimer-Jehle, 2023). The cross-impact ratings from step 4C are summed up for each descriptor considering the signs and strength ratings. The impact sum expresses the net balance of the promoting and hindering influences on the descriptor (Weimer-Jehle, 2023).

If any descriptor exhibits a variant that is inconsistent (Impact sum < 0), the entire scenario must be deemed inconsistent and therefore dismissed. A scenario is only confirmed as consistent and accepted if the impact sum for each descriptor cannot be improved by altering the currently active variant (Weimer-Jehle, 2023). Because visually checking each scenario is infeasible, the consistency check and the generation of scenarios are done with the ScenarioWizard⁵ software.

Figure 17: Hypothetical example of a Impact Sum matrix (Weimer-Jehle, 2023)

⁵ <https://www.cross-impact.org/index.htm>

Step 4E: Generating consistent scenarios

Using the ScenarioWizard software consistent scenarios can be generated by filling in the cross-impact balance matrix. Essentially, this consistency check results in either a "yes" (the scenario is consistent and usable) or a "no" (the scenario has flaws and must be discarded). While primarily a tool for assessing scenario consistency, the CIB algorithm also facilitates the construction of scenarios. This is achieved through the standard CIB process, which examines all possible combinations of descriptor variants within the scenario space, identifying only those combinations that meet the consistency criteria as valid scenarios. Although the CIB method in principle only distinguishes between consistent and inconsistent scenarios it is important to remember that this assessment relies on cross-impact data derived from expert estimates, which inherently contain uncertainties. This uncertainty stems not only from the subjective nature of translating expert knowledge into a numerical cross-impact scale but also from technical issues like rounding errors when using an integer rating scale for impact strength assessments (Weimer-Jehle, 2023). Therefore, the consistency condition should not be seen as an absolute cutoff but rather approached with a significance threshold for identifying minor inconsistencies. For calculating the acceptable inconsistency threshold the following formula can be used, in which; IC_s is the acceptable inconsistency value and; N is the number of descriptors:

$$IC_s \approx \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{N - 1}$$

(3)

An inconsistency value of 2 means that marginally inconsistent scenarios with an impact sum of up to minus 2 are still considered as acceptable scenarios. After checking the consistency of all possible scenarios, the ScenarioWizard software gives out a tableau of the consistent scenarios that can be used for further enhancement (figure 19).

If the goal of the scenario development is solely to integrate them in a multicriteria decision-making model, then the scenario tableau can be used for section 3.3.4, and step 4F, 4G, and 4H can be skipped.

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Scenario No. 1	Scenario No. 2	Scenario No. 3	Scenario No. 4	Scenario No. 5	Scenario No. 6	Scenario No. 7	Scenario No. 8	Scenario No. 9	Scenario No. 10
A. Government: -A3 'Social party'		A. Government: -A2 'Prosperity party'		A. Government: -A3 'Social party'	A. Government: -A1 'Patriots party'	A. Government: -A3 'Social party'	A. Government: -A1 'Patriots party'		
B. Foreign policy: -B1 Cooperation	B. Foreign policy: -B2 Rivalry	B. Foreign policy: -B1 Cooperation	B. Foreign policy: -B2 Rivalry	B. Foreign policy: -B1 Cooperation	B. Foreign policy: -B2 Rivalry		B. Foreign policy: -B3 Conflict		
C. Economy: -C3 Dynamic				C. Economy: -C2 Stagnant				C. Economy: -C1 Shrinking	
D. Distribution of wealth: -D2 Strong contrasts				D. Distribution of wealth: -D1 Balanced				D. Distribution of wealth: -D2 Strong contrasts	
E. Social cohesion: -E1 Social peace		E. Social cohesion: -E2 Tensions		E. Social cohesion: -E1 Social peace				E. Social cohesion: -E3 Unrest	
F. Social values: -F1 Meritocratic				F. Social values: -F2 Solidarity			F. Social values: -F3 Family		

Figure 18: Hypothetical example of a scenario tableau (Weimer-Jehle, 2023)

Step 4F: Adding visual and narrative elements

The aim of the circular adaptive reuse scenarios is twofold; to integrate them into a multicriteria decision-making model, and to serve as a guiding tool for showing stakeholders of adaptive reuse projects what is possible when pursuing adaptive reuse. To do this, the draft scenarios that come out of the ScenarioWizard software can be enriched with visual and narrative elements. This can be done through stakeholder workshops and interviews. The draft scenarios consist of descriptors, each with one of the three possible variants: strong, medium, and weak. Before a compelling story can be created for the adaptive reuse scenarios more information should be gathered on the background of the scenario. For this, the following template can be used during workshops with participants that dive into the following questions (figure 20 & appendix 2):

- What would a building in this scenario look like before transformation?
- What would a building in this scenario look like after transformation?
- What is the trigger for adaptive reuse in this scenario?
- What would the location and surroundings of this building look like in this scenario?
- For what functions/function changes is this scenario appropriate?
- What type of stakeholders are important in this scenario?
- What would the timeline of this scenario look like?
- Do you know example projects that would fit this scenario?
- What would this scenario be called?

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During the workshops, stakeholders can brainstorm together and fill out a word web for each question. After this information is gathered Artificial Intelligence software like OpenAI's *ChatGPT* can be used to generate storylines and visual images. Generative AI tools like *ChatGPT* and *Veras* can enhance the architectural design process by promoting collaboration and generating context-sensitive, creative design ideas (Ko et al., 2023). By using the power of AI, stakeholders in adaptive reuse projects can quickly generate visual images and scenario descriptions that can effectively bolster the consistent scenarios from the CIB analysis. How to use Generative AI to enhance the adaptive reuse scenarios is described in detail in: (section 4.2.1).

Scenario no. 3.		Name scenario:																																													
<table border="1"> <tr><td>Political and community happenings</td><td>Everybody on board</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Cost</td><td>Very expensive</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Local economy</td><td>Local economic engine</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Market potential</td><td>Great market opportu.</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Social Impact</td><td>Social Heaven</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Accessibility</td><td>Resilient and accessible</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Building Technology</td><td>Technical tour de force</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Environmental impact</td><td>Sustainability heaven</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Indoor environmental quality</td><td>Healthy indoor climate</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Rules and regulations</td><td>Following the rules</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Flexibility and adaptability</td><td>Flexible and adaptable</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Duration and quality</td><td>Strong and durable</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Physical characteristics</td><td>Big and versatile</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Architectural value</td><td>Architectural beauty</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Historical and cultural value</td><td>Preserving history</td><td></td></tr> </table>	Political and community happenings	Everybody on board		Cost	Very expensive		Local economy	Local economic engine		Market potential	Great market opportu.		Social Impact	Social Heaven		Accessibility	Resilient and accessible		Building Technology	Technical tour de force		Environmental impact	Sustainability heaven		Indoor environmental quality	Healthy indoor climate		Rules and regulations	Following the rules		Flexibility and adaptability	Flexible and adaptable		Duration and quality	Strong and durable		Physical characteristics	Big and versatile		Architectural value	Architectural beauty		Historical and cultural value	Preserving history		What would a building in this scenario look like before transformation?	What would a building in this scenario look like after transformation?
Political and community happenings	Everybody on board																																														
Cost	Very expensive																																														
Local economy	Local economic engine																																														
Market potential	Great market opportu.																																														
Social Impact	Social Heaven																																														
Accessibility	Resilient and accessible																																														
Building Technology	Technical tour de force																																														
Environmental impact	Sustainability heaven																																														
Indoor environmental quality	Healthy indoor climate																																														
Rules and regulations	Following the rules																																														
Flexibility and adaptability	Flexible and adaptable																																														
Duration and quality	Strong and durable																																														
Physical characteristics	Big and versatile																																														
Architectural value	Architectural beauty																																														
Historical and cultural value	Preserving history																																														
What is the trigger for adaptive reuse in the scenario? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market volatility • Demographic changes • Technological progress • Changing user needs • Obsolescence • Building decay 	What would the location and surroundings of a building in this scenario look like?	For what function / function changes would this scenario be appropriate?																																													
What type of stakeholders are important in this scenario?	What does the timeline in this scenario look like?	What example projects would fit in this scenario?																																													
Other comments																																															

Figure 19: A template for scenario development workshop (by author)

Step 4G: Connecting scenarios to circular building adaptability strategies

Although adaptive reuse itself can be considered a circular approach, past approaches have not considered the full potential of circular building approaches (van Laar et al., 2024). To make the adaptive reuse scenarios more circular, '*Circular Building Adaptability (CBA)*' strategies can be added to the adaptive reuse scenario from step 6. This way the adaptive reuse scenarios not only serve as input for the multicriteria decision-making model but can also be separately used as a guiding tool for stakeholders that want to make their adaptive reuse project more circular.

For this, the *Circular Building Adaptability* framework by Hamida et al. (2023) is used (M. Hamida et al., 2023). Circular Building Adaptability is defined as: "*the capacity to contextually and physically alter the built environment and sustain its usefulness while keeping the building asset in a closed-reversible value chain*" (M. B. Hamida et al., 2022). Hamida et al. (2023) came up with a framework consisting of 33 CBA strategies divided over 10 determinants: Configuration, Product Dismantlability, Asset Multi-usability, Design, Functional Convertibility, Material Reversibility, Building Maintainability, Resource Recovery, Volume Scalability, Asset Refit-ability (M. Hamida et al., 2023). The list of strategies consists of three types of strategies: '*passive strategies*': which can promote CBA through the building design, '*active strategies*': which foster CBA through the building configuration and user intervention, and '*operational strategies*' which are process-oriented solutions that promote CBA (figure 21). Operational strategies do not require much intervention in the building, and can therefore also be used for the initial intervention direction: '*retain*', in the 1st level decision-making framework (section 3.2).

Stakeholders can map these Circular Building Adaptability strategies to the scenarios of step 4F by using the template in the appendix (appendix 2). A distinction can be made between: strategies that are always applicable in this scenario, strategies that could be applied to this scenario but face barriers, and strategies that can never be applied to this scenario. In: (section 4.2.1) an example of this can be found.

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Strategies for Circular Building Adaptability in Adaptive Reuse	Determinants of Circular Building Adaptability										Enabling and Inhibiting Factors										Evaluation of the Strategies												
	Adaptability Determinants			Interrelated Determinants			Circularity Determinants				Enabling Factors						Inhibiting Factors				Effectiveness of the Strategy in Promoting CBA	Applicability in Practice (e.g. Constructability)	Economic Feasibility	Over all Score (Average)									
	Functional Convertibility	Volume Scalability	Asset Refit-Ability	Configuration Flexibility	Product dismantlability	Asset Multi-Usability	Design Regularity	Material Reversibility	Building Maintainability	Resource Recovery	The building Characteristics	Collaboration & Partnership	Industrial Symbiosis	Presence of Motivated/ Capable Team	Economic Feasibility of Basic Strategies	New Business Models	Policy/Legislative Support	Enabling/Digital Technologies	Location of the Project	Quality and Performance Certification					Social Acceptance	Lack of Expertise	Technical Complexities with Building Products/Materials	Economic Infeasibility of Innovative Strategies	Tendency to Follow Traditional Paradigms	Lack of Data and Warranty on Old Materials	Legal and Legislative Restrictions	Fragmentation of the Building Industry	
Passive Strategies	1. Design Standardization				✗	✗	✗				✗	✗					✗						✗					4	3	5	4		
	2. Separation of the Building Layers (e.g. Separated Walls)	✗			✗	✗					✗												✗					✗	5	3	4	4	
	3. Open the Floor Plan	✗			✗						✗			✗										✗					4	3	3	3.3	
	4. Provision of Multi-Purpose Spaces						✗				✗			✗	✗									✗					4.5	3	4.5	4	
	5. Modularization of Spatial Configuration (Layout)	✗						✗			✗	✗		✗			✗						✗	✗					4.5	3	4	3.8	
	6. Utilization of Standardized Building Products							✗	✗		✗			✗									✗						3	4	4.5	3.8	
	7. Provision of a Core for Building Services	✗									✗													✗	✗					3	3	3	3
	8. Design for Surplus Capacity	✗	✗	✗							✗					✗				✗				✗	✗					4	4	3	3.6
	9. Compartmentalization of Design	✗		✗							✗													✗	✗					4	3	2	3
	10. Design for a Mixed Use (Multifunctionality)	✗									✗			✗	✗		✗		✗				✗	✗	✗	✗			5	3	2	3.3	
Active Strategies	11. Utilization of Secondary (Reused/Recycled) Materials							✗		✗	✗		✗	✗		✗			✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	5	2	1	2.6		
	12. Utilization of Biobased (Biological) Materials							✗		✗	✗		✗		✗				✗	✗	✗		✗						4	3.5	2	3.1	
	13. Utilization of Circular (Reusable/Recyclable) Materials							✗		✗	✗	✗		✗	✗				✗	✗	✗		✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	5	3.5	2	3.5		
	14. Alignment of the Interconnection Between the Floor Plans		✗								✗															✗				3	3	4	3.3
	15. Alignment of the Building Design with the Real Estate Strategy					✗					✗						✗													4	4	5	4.3
	16. Utilization of Adjustable Building Components		✗		✗						✗													✗	✗			✗		4	4.5	3	3.8
	17. Utilization of Dismountable Building Components		✗	✗	✗	✗			✗		✗	✗	✗											✗	✗		✗	✗	5	4.5	4.5	4.6	
	18. Provision of Shareable Spaces						✗				✗				✗				✗						✗		✗			3	3	5	3.6
	19. Utilization of Renewable Energy Technologies									✗	✗		✗					✗	✗	✗	✗			✗						3	5	5	4.3
	20. Enabling the Use of Natural Lighting/Ventilation									✗	✗									✗				✗						4	3	4	3.6
Operational Strategies	21. Utilization of Flexible and Integrated Installations (e.g. Integrated MEPs, Plug-and-Play)			✗	✗			✗															✗	✗				✗	4	5	5	4.6	
	22. Utilization of Water Recovery System									✗										✗				✗	✗			✗	5	3	4	4	
	23. Provision of Shareable Facilities						✗				✗			✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗			✗						5	5	5	5	
	24. Application of (or update of) Material Passports					✗		✗	✗		✗	✗	✗				✗			✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	5	5	3	4.3	
	25. Procurement of the Service of Building Products			✗		✗		✗	✗		✗																✗		4	2.5	2	2.8	
	26. Selective Dismantling							✗			✗	✗		✗	✗								✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	5	2	2.5	3.2	
	27. Send Back Discarded Material for Reuse/Recycling							✗			✗	✗		✗	✗					✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	5	4	3	4	
	28. Repurpose Old Building Materials/Products							✗			✗	✗		✗	✗					✗	✗		✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	5	4	2	3.6	
	29. Product Exchange					✗		✗			✗	✗		✗	✗	✗				✗	✗		✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	5	2	3	3.3	
	30. Implementation of Proactive/Predictive Maintenance								✗							✗		✗					✗	✗			✗		4	4.5	3	3.8	
	31. Repair of Old Building Components										✗			✗	✗								✗	✗	✗		✗		4.5	4	4	4.2	
	32. Preservation of Monumental/Old Parts								✗	✗		✗	✗										✗	✗					4.5	5	2	3.8	
	33. Utilization of Rented-Second-Hand Products from CE Marketplace				✗			✗			✗	✗		✗		✗		✗								✗	✗	✗	4.5	2	3.5	3.3	

Legend	Literature-Based Strategy/Factor	Literature- and Practice-Based Strategy/Factor	Practice-Based Strategy/Factor	CO-Creation-Based Strategy/Factor	Co-Creation-Based Linking	Theory-Practice-Based Linking	Excluded Connection by Participants	Revised Text in Workshop 2
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Figure 20: A Guiding framework for circular building adaptability in adaptive reuse by (M. Hamida et al., 2023)

3.4.5. Step 5: Quantify the objectives and criteria based on the preferences of the stakeholders

After the objectives and criteria are formulated and the scenarios have been generated, the next step in the decision-making process is to capture the stakeholder's degree of importance of the objectives. To pick the most appropriate adaptive reuse scenario for a project, it is important that the preferences of the stakeholders are reflected in the outcomes of the decision model. First, the objectives and the criteria have to be weighted based on importance. In multicriteria decision-making, selecting an appropriate weighting method is crucial for accurately reflecting the importance of each criterion and thus ensuring the decision aligns with stakeholders' priorities and objectives. Among the different weighting methods available, ranging from simple rank ordering to sophisticated mathematical models (Zardari et al., 2015), the Analytical Hierarchy Process stands out for its structured, hierarchical approach to decision-making (Saaty, 1990). We have opted for the AHP method due to its robust framework that not only facilitates a systematic comparison of criteria but also incorporates stakeholder judgments in a way that is both comprehensive and coherent. Moreover, its ability to check the consistency of stakeholders' judgments ensures reliability in the decision-making process (Saaty, 1990). This methodological choice is driven by our aim to achieve a balanced and well-substantiated decision framework that aligns with the complex and multi-faceted nature of decision-making in adaptive reuse projects. The Analytical Hierarchy Process consists of three steps: pairwise comparison of the criteria and objectives, computing the weights, and checking the consistency (Zardari et al., 2015).

Pairwise comparison (AHP)

To weigh the criteria and objectives, the importance of one relative to another needs to be evaluated. This comparison is done based on the 9-point Likert scale developed by (Saaty, 1990)(figure 22). Each pair is assessed by stakeholders using Saaty's fundamental scale of absolute numbers, which ranges from 1 to 9, where 1 signifies equal importance, and 9 denotes extreme superiority of one element over the other. Intermediate values represent varying levels of importance between the two extremes. In the initial stage of comparisons, if one aspect is deemed moderately more significant than another aspect, the value assigned to this aspect is 3, with the corresponding reciprocal, being: $\frac{1}{3}$. This evaluation continues with other pairs on the same level to construct the initial 3x3 matrix. Upon completing this first level, the focus shifts to the second level, where only elements linked to the same root in the preceding level are compared. For example, at this second level, 'Cost' and 'Market Potential' are analyzed together

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because they both fall under the overarching category of 'Economy'. For the pairwise comparison, the following equation is used:

(Si & Marjanovic-Halburd, 2018)

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{n1} & \dots & a_{nn} \end{bmatrix} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 1/9 \leq a_{i,j} \leq 9 \text{ if } i \sim j \\ a_{i,j} = 1, \text{ if } i = j \end{array} \right\}$$

(4)

Figure 21: Comparison scale for the pairwise comparison adapted from (Si & Marjanovic-Halburd, 2018)

Computing the weights of objectives

Once these matrices are completed, the weights are derived by normalizing the values within each column to reflect the importance of criteria relative to one another. The weights are computed by adding up the values in each column 'i', then dividing each element a_{kj} by the total of that column, represented as $\sum a_{kj}$ for n iterations, and subsequently dividing the sum of normalized scores for each row 'j' by the number of criteria 'n' in each matrix.

$$w_k = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{a_{kj}}{\sum_{i=1}^n a_{ij}} \text{ for } k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$$

(5)

The normalized scores are then aggregated to determine the final weights, providing a structured and systematic approach to decision-making that accommodates both qualitative assessments and quantitative analyses.

Checking the consistency

In the Analytical Hierarchy Process, the consistency check plays a fundamental role in ensuring the reliability and accuracy of the decision-making process (Saaty, 1990). Consistency refers to the degree to which decision-makers judgments in pairwise comparisons adhere to logical principles and avoid contradictions. To conduct the consistency check, the AHP utilizes the concept of the consistency ratio (CR), which evaluates the coherence of judgments provided by decision-makers. This ratio is calculated by comparing the consistency index (CI) to a randomly generated value known as the random index (RI), which corresponds to the level of consistency expected by chance alone for matrices of a given size (table 2). If the CR exceeds a predefined threshold, typically 0.10, it indicates that the judgments provided are not sufficiently consistent and may require revision or further scrutiny.

Table 2: Random Index (RI) for different number of criteria

Number of criteria / objectives	RI
2	0
3	0.58
4	0.9
5	1.12

For example, if a stakeholder asserts that *Flexibility and Adaptability* hold greater importance than *Durability and Quality*, and *Durability and Quality* is prioritized over *Physical characteristics*, it is logically expected that the same stakeholder would prioritize *Flexibility and Adaptability* over *Physical characteristics*. The consistency ratio serves as a metric to assess the coherence of such pairwise comparisons. When the CR falls below 0.10, it signifies a reasonable level of consistency in the judgments provided. Conversely, if the CR exceeds 0.10, it indicates inconsistent judgments. This analytical process should be conducted separately for each matrix and each stakeholder group to ensure thoroughness and accuracy in decision-making. The consistency ratio CR is defined as follows:

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RI}$$

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Here, CI represents the Consistency Index, while RI stands for the Random Index. The Random Index corresponds to the average consistency index derived from 500 reciprocal matrices populated with values from the fundamental scale of 1-9, which can be generated automatically. Table 2 outlines the RI values for various scenarios based on the number of criteria incorporated into a specific matrix. The calculation of the consistency index is as follows: $CI = \lambda_{max} - n / n - 1$. Here, λ_{max} denotes the maximum eigenvalue of each comparison matrix, which can also be computed automatically. The consistency index can be calculated using the following formula:

$$CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1}$$

(7)

The consistency check is vital because inconsistent judgments can undermine the validity of the decision-making process, leading to suboptimal outcomes and potentially eroding stakeholder trust. By enforcing consistency checks, the AHP promotes robust decision-making by encouraging decision-makers to critically assess their judgments and ensure coherence and reliability throughout the analytical process.

3.4.6. Step 6: Decide on the most appropriate circular adaptive reuse scenario

Once the stakeholders' preferences have been captured, including the objectives and their respective weights, the subsequent step involves evaluating the adaptive reuse scenarios based on these preferences. This last phase of the multicriteria decision-making framework is dedicated to decision analysis. Here, the performance of each scenario across the established objectives is integrated with the assigned weights from the prior step to derive a comprehensive global performance score for each scenario. This score facilitates the ranking of scenarios, streamlining the final decision-making process. Various methods can be employed for this integration, such as simple additive aggregation, Analytical Hierarchy Process, Promethee, and Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS), depending on the specific requirements and contexts within different domains (Zanakis et al., 1998).

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For this MCDM framework, the Fuzzy TOPSIS method is chosen for the ranking of the scenarios. The Fuzzy Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) method is employed in decision-making processes where there is uncertainty or ambiguity in the data or criteria (Dymova et al., 2013). Unlike traditional TOPSIS, which operates under crisp or precise data, Fuzzy TOPSIS accommodates fuzzy sets, allowing for the representation of imprecise or vague information (Dymova et al., 2013). The Fuzzy TOPSIS method is designed to select the best alternative from a set of options based on their distance from the ideal solution and proximity to the negative solution. Fuzzy TOPSIS is particularly useful when dealing with subjective judgments, incomplete information, or when criteria cannot be precisely quantified (Dymova et al., 2013). The key difference lies in the handling of uncertainty; Fuzzy TOPSIS employs fuzzy logic to model uncertainty and vagueness, providing a more robust and flexible approach to decision-making in complex and uncertain environments (Dymova et al., 2013). This method fits well with the qualitative nature of the adaptive reuse scenarios in which the scenarios consist of 15 descriptors that can contain a weak, medium, or strong variant. Below the steps of the Fuzzy TOPSIS method are explained:

Define the decision matrix

Start by constructing a decision matrix D , where each row represents a scenario and each column represents an objective. Let m denote the number of scenarios and n denote the number of objectives:

$$D = \begin{pmatrix} X_{11} & \cdots & X_{1n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ X_{m1} & \cdots & X_{mn} \end{pmatrix}$$

(8)

Transform the decision matrix into a fuzzy decision matrix - Fuzzification

To transform the decision matrix into a fuzzy decision matrix, you start with a matrix containing linguistic variables. In the case of the adaptive reuse scenarios, the matrix consists of scenarios that contain a strong, medium, or weak variant, for each objective (see Figure 16). To transform the linguistic variables into fuzzy variables a conversion method is needed. For this a triangular fuzzy method is used that represents the range of the linguistic variable, in numbers using the minimum value, the maximum value, and the most common value, on a 1-9 conversion scale (Xu, 2007). Table 3-5 portrays an example of this fuzzification process in which the linguistic variables are converted into fuzzy numbers.

Table 3: an example decision matrix with linguistic variables

	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Environmental Impact	Strong	Weak	Weak
Indoor Environmental quality	Strong	Strong	Weak
Cost	Weak	Medium	Strong

Table 4: An example conversion table for converting linguistic variables into fuzzy numbers

	Minimum value	Most common	Maximum value
Weak	1	3	5
Medium	3	5	7
Strong	5	7	9

Table 5: An example fuzzy decision matrix

	Scenario 1			Scenario 2			Scenario 3		
Environmental impact	5	7	9	1	3	5	1	3	5
Indoor environmental quality	5	7	9	5	7	9	1	3	5
Cost	1	3	5	3	5	7	5	7	9

Normalize the decision matrix

The normalization of a fuzzy decision matrix can be accomplished through several methods, with the goal of converting all values to a common scale, typically [0,1] (Xu, 2007). One common approach is to divide each fuzzy number by the maximum fuzzy number in its column, ensuring that the highest value (in terms of possibility and feasibility) in each criterion reaches the maximum normalized value of one. This approach maintains the relative proportions of the fuzzy numbers, preserving the inherent uncertainty of the original data while allowing for an equitable aggregation and comparison across different objectives and scenarios (Xu, 2007). This means that the fuzzy numbers in the maximum column (see Table 4) are normalized based on the highest value within that column. The normalization is done based on the following formula:

$$x_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij} - \min(x_j)}{\max(x_j) - \min(x_j)} \quad (9)$$

Construct the Weighted Normalized Decision Matrix

For the construction of the weighted normalized fuzzy decision matrix the objective weights from the pairwise comparison are used (see section 3.4.5). To form the weighted matrix the weights are multiplied with the normalized fuzzy numbers to generate the weighted normalized decision matrix.

$$R_{ij} = x_{ij} \times w_j \quad (10)$$

Determine Fuzzy Ideal and Negative-Ideal Solutions

In the Fuzzy TOPSIS method, the concepts of FPIS (Fuzzy Positive Ideal Solution) and FNIS (Fuzzy Negative Ideal Solution) are pivotal for ranking and selecting the best option among alternatives. The FPIS represents an ideal solution where each objective is at its optimal fuzzy value. Conversely, the FNIS represents the least desirable outcomes, with each objective at its least advantageous fuzzy value (Xu, 2007). These concepts are constructed by identifying the best and worst possible fuzzy scores across all alternatives for each criterion. The proximity of each alternative to these idealized fuzzy solutions is then calculated to determine their relative ranks. The alternative closest to the FPIS and farthest from the FNIS is considered the best option.

FPIS (A*): The FPIS is calculated by selecting the best values for each objective from the set of scenarios. If x_{ij} represents the fuzzy evaluation of the i-th alternative with respect to the j-th criterion, the FPIS for each criterion can be represented as:

$$A_j^* = \begin{cases} \max_i x_{ij} & \text{if the criterion is beneficial} \\ \min_i x_{ij} & \text{if the criterion is non – beneficial} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

FNIS (A-): Conversely, the FNIS is determined by selecting the worst values for each objective. If x_{ij} represents the fuzzy evaluation of the i-th alternative with respect to the j-th criterion, the FNIS for each criterion can be represented as:

$$A_j^- = \begin{cases} \min_i x_{ij} & \text{if the criterion is beneficial} \\ \max_i x_{ij} & \text{if the criterion is non – beneficial} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Calculate the Distance to Ideal Solutions

The distances from each scenario to the FPIS (d_i^*) and FNIS (d_i^-) are calculated using the fuzzy distance measure which in this case is the Euclidian distance. The formulas for these distances, using the Euclidean distance are:

$$\text{Distance to FPIS } (d_i^*): d_i^* = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (x_{ij} - A_j^*)^2} \quad (13)$$

$$\text{Distance to FNIS } (d_i^-): d_i^- = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (x_{ij} - A_j^-)^2} \quad (14)$$

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Here, n is the number of objectives, x_{ij} is the fuzzy score of the i -th scenario on the j -th objective, and A_j^* is the score of the FPIS on the j -th objective, and A_j^- is the score of the FNIS on the j -th objective.

Using these distances, each alternative's relative closeness to the ideal solution is calculated, which is used to rank the alternatives. The alternative with the shortest distance to the FPIS and the longest distance from the FNIS is considered the optimal choice.

Compute the Closeness Coefficient:

In the Fuzzy TOPSIS method, the closeness indicator is a key metric used to rank the scenarios based on their proximity to the ideal solution. It quantifies how close each scenario is to the Fuzzy Positive Ideal Solution (FPIS) and how far it is from the Fuzzy Negative Ideal Solution (FNIS). This indicator is measured using the formula:

$$CI_i = \frac{d_i^-}{d_i^* + d_i^-} \quad (15)$$

Where d_i^* is the distance of the i -th alternative from the FPIS, and d_i^- is its distance from the FNIS. The closeness indicator, CI_i , ranges from 0 to 1, where a value closer to 1 indicates that the scenario is closer to the FPIS and farther from the FNIS, making it a more preferable option. This measure effectively integrates both the "goodness" and "badness" measures into a single indicator.

Rank the Scenarios

Finally, the scenarios can be ranked based on the Closeness Coefficient indicator (CI_i). The scenario with the highest CI_i value is ranked as the best choice, as it strikes the optimal balance between maximizing desirable traits and minimizing undesirable ones, according to the objectives established in the decision matrix.

By calculating this indicator for each scenario, decision-makers of adaptive reuse projects can effectively rank the options from most to least preferable. This ranking process is critical as it gives stakeholders a clearer overview of which scenario best aligns with their preferences and objectives. The closeness indicator succinctly captures the essence of the scenario's

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performance across all objectives, thus facilitating a more informed and consensus-based decision-making process. Stakeholders can see not only which options are generally better but also how closely each option meets the ideal set of conditions. This methodological approach enhances transparency and aids stakeholders in making decisions that are robust, well-informed, and closely aligned with their strategic goals.

3.4.7. Step 7: Decide on the next life of building products

The last step in the decision-making framework is to decide on the next life of building products. This can be done based on the 3rd level decision-making framework (figure 24). After the most appropriate circular adaptive reuse scenario is chosen, the stakeholders have a sense of what their future project might look like. Based on the scenario building specific requirements can be drawn up. For example, in an adaptive reuse scenario where there is a specific focus on improving indoor environmental conditions, the current ventilation system might not fit the user requirements anymore and needs to be replaced. However, in a scenario where there is no specific focus on improving indoor conditions, the current ventilation system could still meet the user requirements.

Figure 22: 3rd level decision-making framework (by author)

The product-level decision-making framework is based on the R-ladder (Minguez et al., 2021), and guides stakeholders to decide on the next 'life' of building products. In this conceptual model 9 potential end-states for building products are distinguished based on the R-strategies from the R-ladder: *Do nothing (refuse)*, *upgrade product on-site (repair / refurbish)*, *remanufacture for the same function (remanufacture)*, *repurpose on-site (repurpose)*, *repurpose off-site (repurpose)*, *remanufacture for different function (remanufacture)*, *recycle (recycle)* and *recover (recover)*. This conceptual model systemizes the decision-making process for reusing building products and can be used for both adaptive reuse and renovation. A practical example of how the product-level decision-making framework works is explained in deliverable 2.2.

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Figure 23: Conceptual framework of the 3rd level decision-making framework (by author)

4. Practical implementation of the decision-making framework

To demonstrate the functionality of the decision-making framework, a concise fictional case study is outlined. This example illustrates a fictional situation where an external user independently applies the framework to their project using the stepwise approach outlined in: (section 3.1.2). The scenarios used in this illustrative example were developed through a series of expert workshops and can be used as default scenarios in the decision-making framework. More comprehensive cases of real-world implementation will be documented as part of the outcomes from Reincarnate Work Package 5. In this work package, the decision-making framework will be employed in various Reincarnate demonstration projects (see section 6).

Figure 24: Proposed decision-making framework for the adaptive refurbishment and renovation of real estate assets (by author)

4.1. 1st level decision-making framework – Implementation example

4.1.1. Step 1: Map the current condition, utilization, and potential reward of the building

For the practical implementation example, a case study is used from Langston and Smith (2012), to show how the 1st level decision-making framework would work for an adaptive reuse case (Langston & Smith, 2012). For filling in the weighting and performance rating of the criteria and elements the IconCUR assessment worksheet filled in for the former Bushells Tea Company building located at 88 George Street in Sydney, was copied (Langston & Smith, 2012).

However, if the 1st level decision-making framework is used for a new project the first step is to identify stakeholders and weigh the criteria. In the 1st level decision-making framework, 5 common stakeholders are included: *building owner, building user, facility manager, sponsor financier, and community*, but the framework is flexible for the inclusion of more stakeholders if necessary. Each stakeholder does the weighing of the sub-criteria based on the weighing percentage method (see Formula 1). The weighing of the sub-criteria should be done from the perspective of the stakeholder, after which the final weights are determined by taking the average. An example of weighting the sub-criteria is shown in: Tables 7 & 8).

The weighting of the elements for condition, utilization, and collective utility can be done by the stakeholders separately first and then combined together. However, the important weighting of the different stakeholders should be done based on consensus. Although the stakeholders are free to do the weighting of elements how they like, a weighting suggestion is given for each (see Table 6).

Table 6: Suggested weighting methods for criteria in the 1st level decision-making framework

Criteria	Weighing suggestion
Condition	The element weighting can be informed by the importance of the construction cost proportional to each element.
Utilization	The element weighting can be informed by the relative magnitude of each zone/space.
Collective utility	The element weighting can be informed by the importance of these goals to overall project success.
Stakeholder interest	The element weighting can be informed by the relative dominance of stakeholders as controlling entities, taking into consideration issues of power, legitimacy, and urgency. This should be based on consensus between all stakeholders

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Table 7: An example of weighting the sub-criteria of the 1st level decision-making framework for 5 stakeholders

	Building owner	Building user	Facility manager	Sponsor financier	community	Final Weight
Condition						
Design standard	50	40	60	55	45	50%
Maintained service level	10	20	30	40	25	25%
Regulatory compliance	10	30	20	30	25	25%
Utilization						
Demand or relevance	20	50	50	40	30	40%
Fitness for purpose	40	45	35	30	50	40%
User satisfaction	20	20	15	15	30	20%
Collective Utility						
Economic performance	20	20	30	10	20	20%
Culture and heritage	25	55	35	45	40	40%
Environmental value	40	50	30	35	45	40%
Stakeholder interest						
Short-term perspective	50	50	45	55	50	50%
Medium-term perspective	15	25	20	30	35	25%
Long-term perspective	10	25	25	25	40	25%

After the weights are determined for all sub-criteria and elements each stakeholder can do the performance rating based on the Likert scale survey (Appendix 1). All stakeholders can fill in the survey separately and the final performance rating is based on the averages of all responses. Based on the weights from the elements, sub-criteria and the ratings from the survey, final scores for condition, utilization and reward are calculated. The final coordinates of the building are portrayed on the 1st level decision-making matrix (Figure 27), and from this the first intervention direction can be determined.

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Table 8: An example of weighting the sub-criteria of the 1st level decision-making framework for 5 stakeholders (2)

	Building owner	Building user	Facility manager	Sponsor financier	community	Final Weight
Condition						
• Structure	20	20	15	20	25	20%
• Exterior envelope	35	25	20	40	30	30%
• Interior finishes / fitout	10	30	15	25	20	20%
• Engineering services	20	25	15	20	20	20%
• External works	10	5	15	10	10	10%
Utilization						
• Internal space	20	25	35	30	35	30%
• External space	5	5	15	15	10	10%
• Outdoor site area	10	10	10	10	10	10%
• Equipment and fitout						30%
• Engineering systems	20	20	30	10	20	20%
Collective Utility						
• Operational viability	35	25	20	40	30	30%
• Locational context	20	20	15	20	25	20%
• Risk and opportunity	20	20	15	15	30	20%
• Asset valuation	20	20	30	10	20	20%
• Profile / mission	10	5	15	10	10	10%
Stakeholder interest						
• Building owner	x	x	x	x	x	40%
• Building user	x	x	x	x	x	20%
• Facility manager	x	x	x	x	x	10%
• Sponsor / financier	x	x	x	x	x	10%
• community	x	x	x	x	x	20%

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Condition	design standard	Maintained service level	regulatory compliance		
	weighting	0.5	0.25	0.25	
Structure	0.2	4	4	4	4
Exterior envelope	0.3	4	4	4	4
Interior finishing	0.2	3	3	4	3.333333
Engineering finishing	0.2	2	3	3	2.666667
External works	0.1	4	3	5	4
	1	3.4	3.5	3.9	3.55
Utilization	demand or relevance	fitness or purpose	user satisfaction		
	weighting	0.4	0.4	0.2	
Internal space	0.3	1	2	2	1.666667
external space	0.1	0	2	0	0.666667
outdoor site area	0.1	0	0	0	0
equipments and fitout	0.3	1	1	0	0.666667
Engineering systems	0.2	1	1	0	0.666667
	1	0.8	1.3	0.6	0.96
Collective utility	economic performance	culture and heritage	environmental values		
	weighting	0.2	0.4	0.4	
Operational viability	0.3	2	2	3	2.333333
locational context	0.2	5	5	1	3.666667
risk and opportunity	0.2	2	4	3	3
asset valuation	0.2	3	5	1	3
profile/ mission	0.1	4	5	2	3.666667
	1	3	3.9	2.1	3
Stakeholder interest	short-term perspective	medium-term perspective	long-term perspective		
	weighting	0.5	0.25	0.25	
buildingowner	0.4	3	4	5	4
buildinguser	0.2	3	2	1	2
facility manager	0.1	5	5	5	5
sponsor/ financier	0.1	5	3	1	3
community	0.2	5	5	5	5
	1	3.8	3.8	3.8	3.8
Reward	2.28				

	condition (x axis)	utilization (y axis)	reward (z axis)
2.263333333			
property status	3.55	0.96	2.28

1st level decision-making assessment sheet

Figure 25: The 1st level decision-making assessment worksheet adapted from Langston and Smith (2012)

4.1.2. Step 2: Decide on the first intervention direction based on the 1st level decision-making framework

Based on the 1st level decision-making matrix a decision can be made for either *Retain*, *Renovation* (Deliverable 2.2), *Deconstruct*, or *Adaptive Reuse*. Based on the coordinates (Condition=3.55, Utilization=0.96, and Reward=2.28), Adaptive Reuse can be determined as the most likely first intervention direction. A *Reward* of 2.28 tells us that there is still an added benefit from an intervention. The relative closeness to the corner also tells us that there is a relative certainty that the decision to go for adaptive reuse is the right decision. Based on this initial intervention direction stakeholders can decide to use the 2nd level decision-making framework for adaptive reuse below, to find out what adaptive reuse scenario best fits with their preferences. Although this conceptual model gives a good impression of what the best intervention direction is based on the current building, stakeholders are encouraged to play around with the input to test the robustness of the outcomes.

Figure 26: An example of the outcome for the 1st level decision-making framework (by author)

4.2. 2nd level decision-making framework - Implementation guideline

4.2.1. Step 3: Define the problem, objectives, and criteria

Following the outcomes of the 1st level decision-making framework, adaptive reuse is chosen as the most appropriate intervention option. The next step is to define the problem, objectives, and criteria for the future building project. The objectives and criteria are both used to develop the adaptive reuse scenarios as well as to assess the scenarios based on the preferences of the stakeholders. The objectives and criteria can be chosen from the pool of criteria given in: (section 3.3.1).

The objectives and criteria for this practical implementation example, are chosen based on a 2-round Delphi questionnaire with experts of adaptive reuse projects. For the first round, participants were asked to rate the importance of the pre-identified objectives and criteria (from the pool of criteria in section 3.3.1) for future adaptive reuse projects on a scale from 0 (=not important at all), to 4 (=very important). In addition, they could also suggest new objectives and criteria to be included.

After the first round, the second round of the Delphi process was initiated. In this round, participants had access to feedback from the earlier questionnaire. This included the average importance levels assigned by all participants, alongside each respondent's own prior responses. They were also able to view comments made by other participants. Participation in this second survey was exclusive to those who had engaged in the first round. The participants of the Delphi study are shown in: (table 9).

Table 9: Participants of the Delphi questionnaire

Job description	Years of experience with adaptive reuse
Building manager municipality	10
Program manager adaptive reuse	29
Associate Architect	7
Senior Architect	14
Consultant	4
Sustainability consultant	8
Circularity consultant	1
Architect/engineer	7
Housing expert	17
Architect	7
Senior consultant circularity	20
Building engineer	5

Based on the results from the Delphi questionnaire the 15 most important objectives were chosen for the scenario development process and decision-making framework. For the

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selection of objectives, it is recommended to select between 9-15 for the scenario development process (Weimer-Jehle, 2023).

Figure 27: The descriptors and objectives chosen for the scenario development process

4.2.1. Step 4: Develop adaptive reuse scenarios OR choose the default adaptive reuse scenarios

In this decision-making framework, stakeholders have the choice between developing their own adaptive reuse scenarios or choosing the default adaptive reuse scenarios. For this practical implementation example, adaptive reuse scenarios have been developed through a combination of the cross-impact balance analysis, and expert workshops. These scenarios will serve as the default scenarios if the stakeholders choose not to develop their own. A detailed description of these scenarios can be found in the appendix (Appendix 3). The scenario development process will be explained below.

Step 4A: Selecting scenario descriptors

The scenario descriptors that are used for the scenario development are based on the 15 most important objectives from the Delphi questionnaire. The key aspect of the descriptors are the objectives. Because CIB analyses are typically performed at a high aggregation level, given the constrained number of descriptors, criteria, and objectives can be combined into one comprehensive descriptor. To form the descriptor, the objective can be taken as a starting point and relevant criteria from the list can be added that support the objective. Based on the objective, criteria, and theme, a description can be written that explains the descriptor. Figure 29 shows an example of the content of the descriptor: Political and Community support. A detailed overview of all the descriptors used for the scenarios can be found in the appendix (appendix 3). For the scenario development process, the following descriptors are used:

- A) Political and Community support
- B) Cost
- C) Local Economy
- D) Market Potential
- E) Social Impact
- F) Accessibility
- G) Building Technology
- H) Environmental Impact
- I) Indoor Environmental Quality
- J) Rules and Regulations
- K) Flexibility and Adaptability
- L) Durability and Quality
- M) Physical Characteristics
- N) Architectural Value
- O) Historic and Cultural Value

Figure 28: Overview of the setup of a descriptor (by author)

Step 4B: Developing future directions

After the descriptors are defined, the future directions of each descriptor can be drawn up in the form of variants. For each descriptor three different variants are established: a strong variant in which the objective within the descriptor is definitely reached, a medium variant in which the objective is partially reached, and a weak variant in which the objective is not reached. For all 15 descriptors, three variants are established including a name, and detailed description of the variant, which can be found in the appendix (appendix 3). It is important to repeat that the variants should be mutually exclusive and collectively exhaustive (Weimer-Jehle, 2023), and should describe a comprehensive image of one future direction of the descriptor. In Figure 30 an example of the descriptor: 'Political and Community support' is given with the corresponding three variants.

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Figure 29: An example of the descriptor: 'Political and Community support' with three different variants (by author)

Step 4C: Identifying relationships

For the identification of the relationships between descriptor variants, the cross-impact balance analysis matrix can be used. For the scenario development in this practical example, the matrix was filled in during a participatory workshop with experts in the field of adaptive reuse. Table 10 shows the experts who participated in the workshop. During the workshop the participants filled in the matrix in groups of two by answering the following questions:

If variant x were to occur for descriptor X, would this promote or hinder variant y for descriptor Y?

This question was answered based on a seven-point cross-impact rating scale (see Figure 17), in which **3** means that variant **x** strongly promotes variant **y**, and **-3** means that variant **x** strongly prohibits variant **y**. Figure 31 shows the completely filled-in cross-impact balance analysis matrix that came out of the workshop.

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Themes	Descriptors	Variants	A1 A2 A3	B1 B2 B3	C1 C2 C3	D1 D2 D3	E1 E2 E3	F1 F2 F3	G1 G2 G3	H1 H2 H3	I1 I2 I3	J1 J2 J3	K1 K2 K3	L1 L2 L3	M1 M2 M3	N1 N2 N3	O1 O2 O3	
Political	A) Political and Community Support	A1: Everybody on board		1 1 1	2 1 0	1 1 0	2 1 -1	0 0 0	3 2 -1	3 3 1	3 2 -2	3 2 1	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	3 3 1	3 2 1	
		A2: Supportive hesitation	1 -1 -2	1 0 0	1 1 1	1 1 1	0 0 0	0 0 0	2 0 -2	3 1 -3	2 0 -1	2 1 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	2 1 1	1 0 -1	
		A3: Lack of support	1 -2 -3	-2 -1 1	-2 -1 1	-1 1 2	-2 -1 2	0 0 0	0 0 0	-1 -2 -3	2 0 -3	1 0 0	-2 1 3	-1 -2 -3	-1 -2 -3	0 0 0	1 1 3	-2 0 3
Economic	B) Cost	B1: Cost efficient	2 2 -2		3 2 0	2 1 1	1 1 -1	0 0 0	3 1 -2	3 3 -2	3 3 -1	3 2 1	3 2 1	3 2 1	0 0 0	3 2 0	3 2 1	
		B2: Moderately costly	1 0 -1		2 1 0	1 1 1	0 0 0	0 0 0	2 0 -3	2 2 -3	2 1 -2	2 1 0	1 0 -1	1 0 -1	0 0 0	0 0 1	1 0 -1	
		B3: Very costly	-2 -1 2		1 1 0	1 1 2	-2 -1 1	0 0 0	1 -2 -3	-2 -3 -3	-2 -2 -3	-1 0 3	-1 -2 -3	-1 -2 -3	0 0 0	-2 1 3	-1 1 3	
	C) Local Economy	C1: Local economic engine	2 2 -2	3 2 1		2 1 -1	1 0 -1	0 0 0	0 0 0	1 0 -1	1 1 0	3 2 1	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	3 2 1	3 2 1	
		C2: Economic activity	1 0 -1	2 1 0		1 1 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 -1 -2	0 0 0	2 1 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	2 0 0	1 0 -1	
		C3: Economic decline	-2 -1 2	1 -1 -3		-2 -1 2	-2 -1 2	0 0 0	0 0 0	-3 -3 -3	0 0 0	-1 1 3	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 1 3	-1 0 3	
D) Market Potential	D1: Great market opportunity	2 1 0	3 2 1	3 2 0		2 1 0	2 1 -1	3 2 -2	3 3 -2	3 2 -1	3 2 1	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	3 2 1	3 2 1		
	D2: Sufficient market opportunity	1 0 0	3 2 1	2 1 0		1 1 0	1 1 -1	2 1 -2	2 1 -2	2 1 -1	2 1 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	2 1 0	2 0 1		
	D3: Limited market prospects	0 0 1	2 1 -2	1 1 0		0 0 0	0 0 0	-2 -1 2	2 0 3	2 0 -3	1 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	1 2 3	0 2 3		
Social	E) Social Impact	E1: Social heaven	3 2 -2	3 2 1	3 2 0	3 1 -2		2 1 0	2 1 0	3 2 -2	3 2 -2	3 2 1	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	3 2 1	3 2 1	
		E2: Socially acceptable	1 1 -1	3 2 -1	2 1 0	2 -1 -1		0 0 0	2 0 -1	2 0 -2	1 1 -1	1 0 -1	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	2 0 0	2 0 1	
		E3: Anti-social	-2 -1 2	2 0 -2	1 0 0	-2 -1 2		-2 -1 1	1 -1 -2	0 -2 -3	-3 -2 -1	-1 1 3	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	-1 1 3	0 2 3	
F) Accessibility	F1: Reachable and accessible	2 1 -2	3 3 1	1 1 0	1 1 0	2 1 0		3 2 2	3 2 -2	0 0 0	3 2 1	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	3 2 1	3 2 1		
	F2: Some accessibility challenges	0 0 0	2 1 0	1 1 0	1 1 0	0 0 0		2 1 0	2 1 -2	0 0 0	1 1 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	2 1 0	1 0 -1		
	F3: Inaccessible	-2 -1 2	1 0 -2	1 1 0	2 2 3	-2 -1 1		1 -1 -2	0 -1 -3	0 0 0	0 1 2	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	1 2 3	-1 1 3		
Technological	G) Building Technology	G1: A technical tour de force	2 1 -1	3 3 1	0 0 0	2 1 0	0 0 0	1 0 -1		3 2 1	3 2 -3	3 2 1	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	3 2 1	3 2 1	
		G2: Technologically sufficient	1 0 0	3 1 1	0 0 0	1 1 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	3 2 0	2 3 0	2 1 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	2 1 0	2 1 0	
		G3: Technologically inadequate	-1 0 2	0 -2 -3	0 0 0	-2 -1 2	0 0 0	-1 0 1		-3 -2 -3	-3 -3 2	0 2 3	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 2 3	1 0 3	
Environmental	H) Environmental Impact	H1: Sustainability heaven	3 2 -2	3 3 2	3 3 0	3 2 0	2 1 0	1 0 -1	3 2 -3		3 2 -3	3 2 1	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	2 2 1	3 2 1	
		H2: Environmentally friendly	2 1 -1	2 2 0	2 1 0	2 1 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	3 1 -3	3 0 -1	3 0 -1	0 1 1	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	1 0 1	1 0 -1	
		H3: Environmentally unfriendly	-3 -1 2	-3 -1 -3	-2 -1 3	-2 -1 2	-2 -1 1	-1 0 1		-3 -2 0	-1 -2 -3	-2 1 3	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 1 3	-1 1 3	
I) Indoor Environmental Quality	I1: Healthy indoor climate	1 0 -1	3 2 1	0 0 0	3 2 0	1 0 0	0 0 0	3 2 -3	3 2 1		3 2 1	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	3 2 1	3 2 1		
	I2: Decent indoor climate	0 0 0	1 0 -1	0 0 0	2 1 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	3 1 -3	3 0 -2	3 0 -2	1 1 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	2 0 2	2 0 1		
	I3: Cold and Loud	-2 -1 2	1 -1 -3	0 0 0	-2 -1 1	0 0 1	0 0 0	-3 -2 0	-3 -3 -3	-2 1 3	-2 1 3	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	1 2 3	1 2 3		
Legal	J) Rules and Regulations	J1: Following the rules	3 3 -3	2 2 1	0 0 0	0 0 0	2 1 -2	2 1 -1	3 3 0	3 2 -3	3 3 -2		3 2 1	3 2 1	0 0 0	3 1 0	3 1 0	
		J2: Overseeable non-compliance	1 1 -1	1 1 -1	0 0 0	0 0 1	1 0 -1	0 0 0	-2 0 1	2 2 -1	1 2 -2		1 0 -1	1 0 -1	0 0 0	2 1 1	2 0 1	
		J3: Regulatory challenges	-3 -2 2	-2 -2 -3	0 0 0	-2 0 2	-1 0 1	-1 0 1	-3 -2 0	-3 -3 0	-1 -1 2		-1 -2 -3	-1 -2 -3	0 0 0	0 1 3	1 2 3	
Architectural / physical	K) Flexibility and Adaptability	K1: Flexible and Adaptable	2 2 0	3 2 1	1 1 0	3 2 0	0 0 0	1 1 -1	2 2 1	3 3 0	2 1 0	3 2 1		3 2 1	0 0 0	3 2 1	3 2 1	
		K2: Moderately flexible	1 0 0	2 1 1	1 1 0	2 1 1	0 0 0	1 0 0	2 1 0	2 2 -1	2 0 0	2 1 0		1 0 -1	0 0 0	2 1 0	2 1 2	
		K3: Fixed and inflexible	-2 -1 2	2 1 1	0 0 1	0 1 2	0 0 0	-1 0 1	2 -1 -2	0 -1 -3	-1 0 1	1 2 3		-1 -2 -3	0 0 0	1 1 3	1 2 3	
	L) Durability and Quality	L1: Strong and durable	2 1 -1	3 2 1	1 1 0	3 2 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	3 2 2	3 2 0	3 2 -2	3 2 1	3 2 1		0 0 0	3 2 1	3 2 1	
		L2: Sufficiently durable	1 0 0	1 1 -1	0 0 1	2 1 1	0 0 0	0 0 0	1 0 -1	2 0 -1	2 0 -1	2 1 2	1 0 -1		0 0 0	2 0 -1	2 1 2	
		L3: Poor building quality	-3 -2 3	0 0 0	-1 -1 2	1 1 2	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 -1 -3	0 -1 -3	-3 -1 0	-1 1 3	-3 -2 -1		0 0 0	-1 1 3	1 2 3	
M) Physical Characteristics	M1: Big and versatile	2 1 -1	3 2 1	2 1 0	2 1 0	1 0 0	0 0 0	3 3 3	3 2 -1	3 2 -1	3 2 1	0 0 0	0 0 0		3 2 1	3 2 1		
	M2: Medium size building	0 0 0	2 1 0	1 1 0	1 1 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	2 2 1	3 2 -2	2 1 -1	2 1 2	0 0 0	0 0 0		2 1 2	2 1 2		
	M3: Small and compact	-2 -1 2	1 0 -2	0 0 0	0 1 2	0 0 1	0 0 0	1 0 -1	2 1 -2	2 1 -1	-1 1 3	0 0 0	0 0 0		1 2 3	1 2 3		
Cultural	N) Architectural Value	N1: Architectural beauty	1 1 0	3 2 0	1 1 -1	2 1 0	2 1 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	-2 0 2	-2 -1 0	3 2 1	0 0 0	3 2 1	0 0 0		3 1 0	
		N2: Some architectural value	0 0 0	2 1 0	1 0 0	1 1 0	1 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	2 1 0	1 0 0	2 0 -1	0 0 0	1 0 -1	0 0 0		1 0 1	
		N3: Lacking architectural identity	-1 0 1	-2 -2 -3	0 0 2	0 0 2	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	3 2 0	2 1 0	0 1 3	0 0 0	-1 -2 -3	0 0 0		0 1 3	
	O) Historic and Cultural value	O1: Preserving history	2 1 -1	3 2 1	1 1 0	2 1 0	2 1 -1	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	-1 0 0	3 2 -2	3 2 1	0 0 0	3 2 1	0 0 0	3 1 -1	
		O2: Attention to history	1 1 0	2 1 0	1 1 0	1 1 0	1 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	-2 -1 1	1 0 -1	0 0 0	1 0 -1	0 0 0	2 1 1		
		O3: Ignoring history	-2 -1 1	-1 -1 -3	0 0 2	0 0 2	-2 -1 2	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	1 0 0	3 2 -3	0 1 2	-1 -2 -3	0 0 0	0 1 3		

Figure 30: The filled out cross-impact balance matrix from the scenario development workshop (by author)

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Table 10: Workshop participants

Job description	Years of experience with adaptive reuse
Building manager municipality	10
Program manager adaptive reuse	29
Associate Architect	7
Senior Architect	14
Consultant	4
Sustainability consultant	8
Circularity consultant	1
Architect/engineer	7
Financial Advisor	8
Senior Advisor National government	10

Step 4D: Constructing scenarios

After the cross-impact balance matrix is filled in, the ScenarioWizard software can be used for the construction of scenarios. The ScenarioWizard software was developed to perform CIB analysis and has been used, tested and further developed in numerous application projects and method experiments (Weimer-Jehle, 2023). ScenarioWizard for Windows systems is available as a free download⁶. A manual of the software can also be found that describes in detail how the software works, and how scenarios can be constructed. The project file of the default scenarios that are used in this practical example are also available in the appendix (Appendix 4), which can be loaded into the software.

Figure 31: Overview of the ScenarioWizard application⁵

⁶ https://www.cross-impact.org/english/CIB_e_ScW.htm

Step 4E: Generating consistent scenarios

Through the use of the ScenarioWizard software, consistent scenarios can be generated. Based on: (Formula 3) a max inconsistency value of 2 is calculated on the basis of 15 descriptors. An inconsistency value of 2 means that marginally inconsistent scenarios with an impact sum of up to minus 2 are still considered as acceptable scenarios. Based on the input of the CIB matrix and an inconsistency value of 2, the ScenarioWizard software gives back 179 consistent scenarios. A scenario tableau can be generated of the consistent scenarios. However, because 179 scenarios do not fit on the tableau, figure 35 shows 15 of these scenarios. These consistent draft scenarios can be integrated into the multicriteria decision framework in: (section 4.4.2). However, it is advised to not work with a high number of scenarios and to keep the number of scenarios between 4 and 20 (Weimer-Jehle, 2023). For practical reasons, 15 of the 179 scenarios are selected for inclusion in the multicriteria decision framework and for further enhancement in steps 4F and 4G. The 15 scenarios are selected through the selection manager tab in the ScenarioWizard software, by looking at the distance between scenarios. A scenario diversity score of 6 is applied, which means that the scenarios differ in a minimum of six descriptors. This way scenarios with a lot of similarities are avoided, and the scenario portfolio is relatively diverse.

Figure 32: Overview of the evaluation options settings in the ScenarioWizard application⁵

Figure 33: Overview of the selection manager setting in the ScenarioWizard application⁵

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Scenario No. 1	Scenario No. 2	Scenario No. 3	Scenario No. 4	Scenario No. 5	Scenario No. 6	Scenario No. 7	Scenario No. 8	Scenario No. 9	Scenario No. 10	Scenario No. 11	Scenario No. 12	Scenario No. 13	Scenario No. 14	Scenario No. 15	
Political and Community support: Lack of support	Political and Community support: Everybody on board	Political and Community support: Lack of support	Political and Community support: Everybody on board	Political and Community support: Supportive hesitations	Political and Community support: Lack of support			Political and Community support: Supportive hesitations	Political and Community support: Lack of support	Political and Community support: Everybody on board	Political and Community support: Supportive hesitations	Political and Community support: Everybody on board	Political and Community support: Supportive hesitations	Political and Community support: Lack of support	
Cost: Very costly	Cost: Cost efficient		Cost: Very costly	Cost: Moderately costly		Cost: Very costly	Cost: Cost efficient		Cost: Very costly	Cost: Cost efficient	Cost: Very costly	Cost: Moderately costly	Cost: Cost efficient		
Local Economy: Economic decline	Local Economy: Local economic engine	Local Economy: Economic activity	Local Economy: Economic decline		Local Economy: Local economic engine	Local Economy: Economic activity	Local Economy: Local economic engine			Local Economy: Economic decline	Local Economy: Economic activity	Local Economy: Local economic engine			
Market Potential: Limited market prospects	Market Potential: Great market opportunity	Market Potential: Sufficient market opportunity	Market Potential: Limited market prospects	Market Potential: Great market opportunity	Market Potential: Sufficient market opportunity		Market Potential: Great market opportunity		Market Potential: Limited market prospects	Market Potential: Sufficient market opportunity	Market Potential: Limited market prospects	Market Potential: Great market opportunity			
Social Impact: Anti-social	Social Impact: Social heaven	Social Impact: Socially acceptable	Social Impact: Anti-social				Social Impact: Socially acceptable	Social Impact: Social heaven	Social Impact: Socially acceptable	Social Impact: Anti-social		Social Impact: Socially acceptable	Social Impact: Anti-social		
Accessibility: Inaccessible	Accessibility: Reachable and accessible	Accessibility: Some accessibility challenges		Accessibility: Inaccessible				Accessibility: Some accessibility challenges		Accessibility: Inaccessible	Accessibility: Reachable and accessible	Accessibility: Inaccessible			
Building Technology: Technologically inadequate	Building Technology: Technologically sufficient	Building Technology: Technologically inadequate	Building Technology: A technical tour de force		Building Technology: Technologically sufficient	Building Technology: A technical tour de force	Building Technology: Technologically sufficient	Building Technology: Technologically inadequate	Building Technology: A technical tour de force	Building Technology: Technologically sufficient	Building Technology: A technical tour de force	Building Technology: Technologically inadequate		Building Technology: Technologically sufficient	
Environmental Impact: Environmentally unfriendly	Environmental Impact: Sustainability heaven	Environmental Impact: Environmentally unfriendly		Environmental Impact: Environmentally friendly	Environmental Impact: Environmentally unfriendly	Environmental Impact: Sustainability heaven		Environmental Impact: Environmentally unfriendly		Environmental Impact: Sustainability heaven	Environmental Impact: Environmentally unfriendly		Environmental Impact: Environmentally friendly		
Indoor Environmental Quality: Cold and Loud	Indoor Environmental Quality: Healthy indoor climate	Indoor Environmental Quality: Cold and Loud	Indoor Environmental Quality: Decent indoor climate	Indoor Environmental Quality: Healthy indoor climate	Indoor Environmental Quality: Decent indoor climate	Indoor Environmental Quality: Healthy indoor climate	Indoor Environmental Quality: Decent indoor climate	Indoor Environmental Quality: Cold and Loud	Indoor Environmental Quality: Healthy indoor climate		Indoor Environmental Quality: Cold and Loud		Indoor Environmental Quality: Healthy indoor climate		
Rules and Regulations: Regulatory challenges	Rules and Regulations: Following the rules	Rules and Regulations: Regulatory challenges	Rules and Regulations: Following the rules	Rules and Regulations: Overseeable non-compliance	Rules and Regulations: Regulatory challenges	Rules and Regulations: Overseeable non-compliance	Rules and Regulations: Regulatory challenges		Rules and Regulations: Overseeable non-compliance		Rules and Regulations: Regulatory challenges		Rules and Regulations: Regulatory challenges		
Flexibility and Adaptability: Fixed and inflexible	Flexibility and Adaptability: Flexible and Adaptable		Flexibility and Adaptability: Moderately flexible	Flexibility and Adaptability: Flexible and Adaptable		Flexibility and Adaptability: Fixed and inflexible	Flexibility and Adaptability: Flexible and Adaptable	Flexibility and Adaptability: Moderately flexible	Flexibility and Adaptability: Fixed and inflexible	Flexibility and Adaptability: Flexible and Adaptable					
Durability and Quality: Poor building quality	Durability and Quality: Strong and durable			Durability and Quality: Sufficiently durable	Durability and Quality: Strong and durable		Durability and Quality: Poor building quality	Durability and Quality: Strong and durable							
Physical Characteristics: Small and compact	Physical Characteristics: Medium size building		Physical Characteristics: Big and versatile			Physical Characteristics: Medium size building		Physical Characteristics: Small and compact			Physical Characteristics: Big and versatile	Physical Characteristics: Medium size building	Physical Characteristics: Big and versatile	Physical Characteristics: Small and compact	
Architectural Value: Lacking architectural identity	Architectural Value: Architectural beauty	Architectural Value: Some architectural value	Architectural Value: Architectural beauty	Architectural Value: Lacking architectural identity	Architectural Value: Architectural beauty		Architectural Value: Lacking architectural identity	Architectural Value: Architectural beauty	Architectural Value: Lacking architectural identity	Architectural Value: Architectural beauty	Architectural Value: Architectural beauty		Architectural Value: Some architectural value	Architectural Value: Architectural beauty	
Historic and Cultural Value: Ignoring history	Historic and Cultural Value: Preserving history			Historic and Cultural Value: Ignoring history	Historic and Cultural Value: Attention to history	Historic and Cultural Value: Ignoring history		Historic and Cultural Value: Preserving history		Historic and Cultural Value: Ignoring history	Historic and Cultural Value: Preserving history		Historic and Cultural Value: Attention to history	Historic and Cultural Value: Ignoring history	

Figure 34: The scenario tableau for the adaptive reuse scenarios (outcomes from the ScenarioWizard software)

Step 4F: Adding visual and narrative elements

Through a participatory workshop with the participants from workshop 1 (Table 10) a second workshop was held to enrich the draft scenarios from the ScenarioWizard software. For this workshop, the template from the appendix can be used (Appendix 2). The participants were split up into groups of two and were asked to fill in the template for all 15 scenarios. After the templates were filled in the participants were asked to present the scenarios and elaborate on how such a scenario would look like in real life. The answers to the 8 questions were recorded together with the description of the variants and were placed in an Excel sheet.

The Excel sheets can then be used to generate storyline descriptions using *OpenAI's ChatGPT4*⁷. For the generation of the storylines for the scenarios, the following prompt was used (figure 36). For the storylines to remain consistent for all scenarios it is recommended to use the same prompt, but change the Excel input. After the scenario storylines are generated make sure that they match the input of the filled-in scenario templates:

Figure 35: An example Input prompt for ChatGPT 4

When all the storylines are generated, ChatGPT4 can also be used to visualize the scenarios. For the visualisation of the scenarios DALL-E was used⁸. DALL-E is an integrated extension within ChatGPT-4 that specializes in generating images based on textual descriptions provided by users. For the generation of images, the scenario storylines were used as input for the prompt. For this, the following prompt was used:

Figure 36: An example input prompt for ChatGPT 4 (2)

⁷ <https://chat.openai.com/?model=gpt-4>

⁸ <https://chat.openai.com/g/g-pmuQfob8d-image-generator>

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Although DALL-E generally works well with transforming prompts into visual output, refinement of the prompts based on the output might be needed to more closely align the visualizations with your expectations. Generating images with ChatGPT involves an iterative process, however, despite the iterative nature of this approach, it is recommended to maintain a consistent structure and style across all prompts for uniformity. After an initial image of the scenario is generated more prompts can be used to portray different perspectives of the scenario. For the adaptive reuse scenarios, the following prompt was used to generate images from the inside point of view:

Figure 37: An example input prompt for ChatGPT 4 (3)

After the storylines and visualization are generated for the scenarios, they can be combined into a comprehensive scenario scorecard. For all 15 scenarios scorecards are created that can be found in the appendix (Appendix 5). Three examples are highlighted (Figure 38-40). The aim of the addition of visual and narrative elements is to serve as a guiding tool for showing stakeholders of adaptive reuse projects what is possible when pursuing adaptive reuse. It is important to note that the visual and narrative elements generated for the scenario scorecards are only one of many possible outcomes, and the scorecards should be tailored to the preferences of the stakeholders. The draft scenarios from step 4E can be directly integrated into the multicriteria decision-making framework, but the addition of narrative and visual elements supports the imaginative capacity of the scenario-building process.

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Scenario no. 17.		Name scenario: Creative Storage Warehouse	
Political and community support	Lack of support		
Cost	Very costly		
Local Economy	Economically limited		
Market Potential	Limited market potential		
Social Impact	Socially limited		
Accessibility	Inaccessible		
Building technology	Technologically limited		
Environmental Impact	Environmentally unfriendly		
Indoor environmental quality	Cold and Loud		
Rules and Regulations	Regulatory challenges		
Flexibility and Adaptability	Flexible and Adaptable		
Quality and Durability	Strong and Durable		
Physical characteristics	Spacious and Versatile		
Architectural value	Lacking archit. identity		
Historic and Cultural value	Ignoring history		
<p>What does the building look like before transformation?</p> <p> Concrete, a lot of space, no insulation</p>	<p>Description</p> <p>In the scenario "Creative Storage Warehouse," a transformation project is highlighted that faces significant challenges, starting with a lack of political and community support ("A3: Lack of support"). This project, characterized as a concrete shell in the outskirts, struggles with issues on various fronts, from the lack of support to financial burdens that are significantly higher than anticipated ("B3: Very Costly"). The economic impact on the local environment is limited ("C3: Economically limited"), while the project has only limited market potential ("D3: Limited market potential"). Socially, the project may even have negative effects, such as increasing housing prices and disrupting social cohesion ("E3: Socially limited").</p> <p>The accessibility of the building leaves much to be desired ("F3: Inaccessible"), and the applied building technologies are outdated and do not meet user requirements ("G3: Technologically limited"). Moreover, little attention is paid to the environmental effects of the building, which primarily consumes energy from non-renewable sources ("H3: Environmentally unfriendly"). The quality of the indoor environment is substandard, with poor insulation and inadequate ventilation ("I3: Cold and Loud").</p> <p>Regulations and the urban master plan form an additional barrier to the project's success ("J3: Challenging regulations"). The building is flexible and adaptable to future needs ("K1: Flexible and adaptable"), has good construction quality ("L1: Strong and Durable"), and is enhanced by its physical properties ("M1: Spacious and Versatile").</p> <p>The lack of architectural identity ("N3: Lack of architectural identity") and the neglect of historical or cultural heritage ("O3: Ignoring history") add to the project's challenges. The scenario outlines a project with potential for creative and cultural uses, such as for artists and creators, but is hindered by many challenges and the need for quick and cheap occupancy. Example projects such as a rental warehouse with exhibition spaces or Ateliercomplex de Besturing in The Hague offer some hope for what is possible, despite the many obstacles.</p>		
<p>What does the building look like after transformation?</p> <p> Built-in system, or remains open / empty</p>			
<p>What is the trigger for adaptive reuse in this scenario?</p> <p> Demand for open space</p>			
<p>What does the location and surroundings of the building look like after transformation?</p> <p> Outside of the city</p>			
<p>For what function/functional changes is this scenario suited?</p> <p> Creative businesses, mixed-space, artists, cultural, makers</p>			
<p>What type of stakeholders are important in this scenario?</p> <p> Large companies, or low-level entrepreneurs</p>			
<p>What does the timeline look like in this scenario?</p> <p> User can get in quickly and with few resources</p>			
<p>Example projects:</p> <p> De Ping-Pong club (Utrecht)</p>			

Figure 38: An example of a circular adaptive reuse scenario scorecard: "Creative Storage Warehouse" (by author)

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Scenario no. 24.		Name scenario: Diamond in the rough	
Political and Community Support	Supportive hesitation		
Cost	Moderately costly		
Local Economy	Local economic engine		
Market Potential	Sufficient market poten.		
Social Impact	Socially limited		
Accessibility	Inaccessible		
Building Technology	Technologically adequate		
Environmental Impact	Environmentally unfriendly		
Indoor Environmental Quality	Cold and Loud		
Rules and Regulations	Regulatory challenges		
Flexibility and Adaptability	Flexible and adaptable		
Quality and Durability	Strong and durable		
Physical Characteristics	Spacious and versatile		
Architectural value	Architectural beauty		
Historic and Cultural value	Preserving history		
<p>What does this building look like before transformation?</p> <p> old, not in use, icon, recognisable, limited access, inflexible, closed</p>	<p>Description:</p> <p>In a scenario where an iconic but no longer used building on the outskirts of the old city center is preparing for transformation, stakeholders navigate a landscape of cautious support and economic efficiency. Despite the hesitations of some key stakeholders ("A2: Supportive hesitation") and the moderate costs ("B2: Moderately costly") that slightly exceed the budget, this project promises to become a ("C1: local economic engine") with an undeniable positive impact on the local economy. Creating jobs, stimulating local businesses, and improving public amenities are just some of the benefits the transformation will bring.</p>		
<p>In this scenario, what does the building look like after transformation?</p> <p> Flexible, open character, high height, upgrade, multi-functional, additional housing, (publicly) accessible</p>	<p>With ("D2: sufficient market potential") located in a diverse and dynamic environment, the building is seen as attractive to a wide range of buyers and tenants, despite some financial risks. However, the project also faces its challenges. It confronts significant obstacles in terms of social impact ("E3: Socially limited"), accessibility ("F3: Inaccessibility"), and environmental impact ("H3: Environmentally unfriendly"), with the current state described as "limited social," "limited accessibility," and "environmentally unfriendly." These shortcomings in the indoor environment ("I3: Cold and Loud"), technological limitations ("G2: Technologically adequate"), and a strict regulatory environment ("J3: Regulatory challenges") require a thoughtful approach to achieve the desired transformation.</p>		
<p>What is the trigger for adaptive reuse in this scenario?</p> <p> Vacant, beautiful location and building, preserve monument</p>	<p>The heart of the transformation lies in the ("K1: flexible and adaptable") nature of the building, supported by ("L1: Strong and durable") and spacious physical features ("M1: Spacious and versatile") that enable the building to be redeveloped into a flexible, open, and multifunctional space. The architectural ("N1: Architectural beauty") and historical value ("O1: preserving history") of the property is not only maintained but also celebrated, enriching the building and its surroundings.</p>		
<p>What does the location of the building and its surroundings look like in this scenario?</p> <p> Edge of old town, surrounded by housing, diverse environment</p>	<p>This transformation is driven by the vacancy of the building, the value of the location, and the desire to preserve a historical monument. With a project duration of approximately 3 to 4 years, the building will be transformed into a vibrant, multifunctional space that combines housing with other uses, making it accessible to the public and a valuable asset to the surrounding community.</p>		
<p>For which functions / function changes is this scenario suitable?</p> <p> housing, multi-use</p>	<p>Inspiration for this project can be found in similar successful transformations, such as the Koepelgevangenis in Arnhem, the Werkspoorfabriek in Utrecht, and the Bijlmerbajes in Amsterdam. These examples show that with the right approach, vision, and collaboration, old buildings can be revitalized, ensuring they are preserved for future generations while also contributing to the livability and dynamism of urban environments.</p>		
<p>What types of stakeholders are particularly important in this scenario?</p> <p> Operator/investor, municipality, local resident</p>	<p>Example projects:</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Koepelgevangenis (Arnhem)</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>De Werkspoorfabriek (Utrecht)</p> </div> </div>		
<p>What does the timeline of a project in this scenario look like?</p> <p> 3/4 years</p>	<p></p>		

Figure 39: An example of a circular adaptive reuse scenario scorecard: "Diamond in the rough" (by author)

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Scenario no. 33.		Name scenario: The Dream																																														
<table border="1"> <tr><td>Political and Community Support</td><td>Everybody on board</td><td>😊😊</td></tr> <tr><td>Cost</td><td>Cost efficient</td><td>😊😊</td></tr> <tr><td>Local Economy</td><td>Local Economic engine</td><td>😊😊</td></tr> <tr><td>Market Potential</td><td>Great Market Potential</td><td>😊😊</td></tr> <tr><td>Social Impact</td><td>Social Heaven</td><td>😊😊</td></tr> <tr><td>Accessibility</td><td>Reachable and accessible</td><td>😊😊</td></tr> <tr><td>Building technology</td><td>Technologically sufficient</td><td>😊</td></tr> <tr><td>Environmental Impact</td><td>Sustainability heaven</td><td>😊😊</td></tr> <tr><td>Indoor Environmental Quality</td><td>Healthy indoor climate</td><td>😊😊</td></tr> <tr><td>Rules and Regulations</td><td>Following the rules</td><td>😊😊</td></tr> <tr><td>Flexibility and Adaptability</td><td>Flexible and Adaptable</td><td>😊😊</td></tr> <tr><td>Quality and Durability</td><td>Strong and durable</td><td>😊😊</td></tr> <tr><td>Physical characteristics</td><td>Physically sufficient</td><td>😊</td></tr> <tr><td>Architectural value</td><td>Architectural beauty</td><td>😊😊</td></tr> <tr><td>Historic and Cultural value</td><td>Preserving history</td><td>😊😊</td></tr> </table>	Political and Community Support	Everybody on board	😊😊	Cost	Cost efficient	😊😊	Local Economy	Local Economic engine	😊😊	Market Potential	Great Market Potential	😊😊	Social Impact	Social Heaven	😊😊	Accessibility	Reachable and accessible	😊😊	Building technology	Technologically sufficient	😊	Environmental Impact	Sustainability heaven	😊😊	Indoor Environmental Quality	Healthy indoor climate	😊😊	Rules and Regulations	Following the rules	😊😊	Flexibility and Adaptability	Flexible and Adaptable	😊😊	Quality and Durability	Strong and durable	😊😊	Physical characteristics	Physically sufficient	😊	Architectural value	Architectural beauty	😊😊	Historic and Cultural value	Preserving history	😊😊			
Political and Community Support	Everybody on board	😊😊																																														
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Architectural value	Architectural beauty	😊😊																																														
Historic and Cultural value	Preserving history	😊😊																																														
<p>What does this building look like before transformation?</p> <p>Beautiful, healthy, young</p>	<p>Description:</p> <p>In the bustling city center, at a prime location, stands a building that is both historically and architecturally valuable. Despite its attractive location, this building has been struggling with vacancy and is now on the verge of a transformation project that is supported by both the local government and the community ("A1: Everyone on board") and is financially feasible ("B1: Cost-efficient"). The project enjoys broad support, with a focus on preserving the architectural and historical value of the building ("N1: Architectural beauty" & "O1: Preserving history") while transforming it to meet current market demands.</p> <p>The positive impact of the project on the local economy cannot be underestimated ("C1: Local economic engine"). By creating jobs and stimulating local economic activities, the project promises to further enhance urban development in the central area. The building itself possesses significant market potential ("D1: Great market potential") due to its location, ensuring low financial risk and high expected returns.</p> <p>Although the social impact of the project is less emphasized, it aims to improve the neighborhood's livability and maintain social cohesion ("E1: Social Heaven"). The accessibility and reachability of the building ("F1: Accessible and Reachable") make it an integral part of the community, easily accessible to everyone.</p> <p>The technological aspects of the building are adequate, though not exceptional ("G2: Technologically sufficient"), with a focus on sustainability ("H1: Sustainability Heaven") and a healthy indoor climate ("I1: Healthy indoor climate"). This ensures that the building not only meets current standards but also promotes the well-being of its users.</p> <p>The project complies with existing regulations ("J1: Following the rules"), and thanks to the flexibility and adaptability ("K1: Flexible and adaptable"), it can easily be adjusted to future needs. Combined with good construction quality ("L1: Strong and Durable") and sufficient physical features ("M2: Physically sufficient"), a swift transformation is possible, leaving the building largely the same but with a renewed function that addresses vacancy and market demand. An example for this scenario is vacant retail spaces being transformed into housing or mixed-use.</p> <p>This scenario illustrates an ideal vision of how a valuable but underutilized building can be transformed to meet contemporary needs while preserving its rich history and contribution to the urban fabric. It embodies a perfect balance between preservation and innovation, economic vitality, and social responsibility, making it a model project in the world of circular building transformations.</p>																																															
<p>In this scenario, what does the building look like after transformation?</p> <p>Almost the same</p>																																																
<p>What is the trigger for adaptive reuse in this scenario?</p> <p>Vacancy and market demand</p>																																																
<p>What does the location of the building and its surroundings look like in this scenario?</p> <p>City centre, prime location</p>																																																
<p>For which functions / function changes is this scenario suitable?</p> <p>Likely no change of function needed</p>	<p>Example projects:</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Former C&A store (Utrecht)</p> </div> </div>																																															
<p>What types of stakeholders are particularly important in this scenario?</p> <p>Owner, tenant</p>																																																
<p>What does the timeline of a project in this scenario look like?</p> <p>Fast</p>																																																

Figure 40: An example of a circular adaptive reuse scenario scorecard: "The Dream" (by author)

Step 4G: Connecting scenarios to circular building adaptability strategies

The enriched scenarios from step 4H can be further enhanced by connecting them to circular building adaptability strategies. For this, the CBA framework by Hamida et al. (2023) can be used that consists of 33 strategies divided over 3 categories: active strategies, passive strategies, and operational strategies (M. Hamida et al., 2023). Through a workshop with stakeholders the scenarios from step 4H can be mapped to the strategies using the template in the appendix (Appendix 4). For this, the strategies are divided into three categories: strategies that are always applicable in this scenario, strategies that could be applied to this scenario but face barriers, and strategies that can never be applied to this scenario.

Figures 43-44 show the 15 scenarios from step 4H and the corresponding strategies. By connecting the scenarios to the circular building adaptability strategies, stakeholders of adaptive reuse projects not only have a better understanding of what the future could look like when it comes to adaptive reuse but also know what strategies can be applied that would make the project even more circular.

D 3.1 Circular decision-making for adaptive refurbishment and renovation of real estate assets

Strategies for Circular Building Adaptability in Adaptive Reuse	Scenario: 1	Scenario: 3	Scenario: 17	Scenario: 24	Scenario: 29	Scenario: 33	Scenario: 45	Scenario: 68	Scenario: 119	Scenario: 121	Scenario: 140	Scenario: 148	Scenario: 168	Scenario: 170	Scenario: 174
1. Design Standardization	✗	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕
2. Separation of the Building Layers (e.g. Separated Walls)	✗	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕
3. Open the Floor Plan	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✗	✕	✕	✕
4. Provision of Multi-Purpose Spaces	✗	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✗	✕	✕	✕
5. Modularization of Spatial Configuration (Layout)	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕
6. Utilization of Standardized Building Products	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✗	✕	✕	✕
7. Provision of a Core for Building Services	✗	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✗	✕	✕	✗	✗	✕	✕	✕
8. Design for Surplus Capacity	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✗	✕	✕	✕	✗	✕	✕	✗
9. Compartmentalization of Design	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✗	✕	✕	✕	✗	✕	✕	✗
10. Design for a Mixed Use (Multifunctionality)	✗	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕
11. Utilization of Secondary (Reused/Recycled) Materials	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕
12. Utilization of Biobased (Biological) Materials	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕
13. Utilization of Circular (Reusable/Recyclable) Materials	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✗	✕	✕	✕
14. Alignment of the Interconnection Between the Floor Plans	✗	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕
15. Alignment of the Building Design with the Real Estate Strategy	✕	✕	✕	✕	✗	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕

Legend:

- ✕ Strategies that can always be applied
- ✕ Strategies that can sometimes be applied
- ✗ Strategies that can never be applied

Figure 41: The circular building adaptability strategies by: (Hamida et al., 2023), mapped to the circular adaptive reuse scenario (1) (by author)

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Strategies for Circular Building Adaptability in Adaptive Reuse	Scenario: 1	Scenario: 3	Scenario: 17	Scenario: 24	Scenario: 29	Scenario: 33	Scenario: 45	Scenario: 68	Scenario: 119	Scenario: 121	Scenario: 140	Scenario: 148	Scenario: 168	Scenario: 170	Scenario: 174
16. Utilization of Adjustable Building Components	✘	✕	✘	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕
17. Utilization of Dismountable Building Components	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✖	✕	✕	✕
18. Provision of Shareable Spaces	✘	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕
19. Utilization of Renewable Energy Technologies	✖	✕	✘	✘	✘	✕	✘	✘	✘	✘	✕	✖	✘	✘	✕
20. Enabling the Use of Natural Lighting/Ventilation	✖	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✖	✖	✖	✖	✕	✘	✘	✘	✘
21. Utilization of Flexible and Integrated Installations (e.g. Integrated MEPs, Plug-and-Play)	✘	✕	✘	✘	✘	✕	✘	✖	✘	✘	✘	✕	✘	✘	✘
22. Utilization of Water Recovery System	✖	✕	✖	✘	✘	✘	✘	✖	✖	✖	✕	✘	✕	✕	✕
23. Provision of Shareable Facilities	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✘	✕	✕	✕	✖	✕	✕	✕
24. Application of (or update of) Material Passports	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕
25. Procurement of the Service of Building Products	✖	✘	✕	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✖	✖	✖	✖	✘
26. Selective Dismantling	✘	✕	✕	✘	✘	✕	✘	✕	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✕
27. Send Back Discarded Material for Reuse/Recycling	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✘	✕	✕	✕
28. Repurpose Old Building Materials/Products	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✕	✘	✖	✘	✘	✘	✖	✘	✘	✘
29. Product Exchange	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘
30. Implementation of Proactive/Predictive Maintenance	✘	✕	✖	✘	✘	✕	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘
31. Repair of Old Building Components	✕	✕	✘	✕	✕	✕	✕	✘	✘	✘	✘	✖	✘	✘	✘
32. Preservation of Monumental/Old Parts	✘	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✘	✖	✘	✘	✖
33. Utilization of Rented-Second-Hand Products from CE Marketplace	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘	✘

Legend:

- ✕ Strategies that can always be applied
- ✘ Strategies that can sometimes be applied
- ✖ Strategies that can never be applied

Figure 42: The circular building adaptability strategies by: (Hamida et al., 2023), mapped to the circular adaptive reuse scenario (2) (by author)

4.2.2. Step 5: Quantify the objectives and criteria based on the preferences of the stakeholders

Pairwise comparison (AHP)

Once the scenarios are created the next step in the process is the quantification of the objectives and criteria based on the preferences of stakeholders. This quantification process is done through the Analytical Hierarchy Process. This comparison is done based on the 9-point Likert scale developed by (Saaty, 1990)(Figure 22). Each pair is assessed by stakeholders using Saaty's fundamental scale of absolute numbers, which ranges from 1 to 9, where 1 signifies equal importance, and 9 denotes extreme superiority of one element over the other. For the practical example the objectives and main criteria from step 3 are compared using the pairwise comparison method for five stakeholders which resulted in the following comparison matrix (Table 11):

Table 11: Pairwise comparison matrix

Pairwise comparison	Building Owner	Building User	Facility Manager	Sponsor / Financier	community	Total
1st level						
Political vs Economic	1/3	1/5	1/7	1/7	5	11/6
Political vs Social	3	1/5	3	5	1/3	21/3
Political vs Technological	1/3	1/3	1/5	3	3	13/8
Political vs Environmental	1	1/5	1/3	5	1/7	11/3
Political vs Legal	1	3	1/5	1/3	3	11/2
Political vs Architectural	1/3	1/5	1/3	3	1/5	4/5
Political vs Cultural	5	1/5	3	5	1/3	25/7
Economic vs Social	5	3	7	9	5	54/5
Economic vs Technological	3	3	1/3	5	1/5	21/3
Economic vs Environmental	5	1/3	3	5	1/5	25/7
Economic vs Legal	3	3	1	3	3	23/5
Economic vs Architectural	3	1/3	3	3	1/5	2
Economic vs Cultural	5	3	3	5	1/5	31/4
Social vs Technological	1/3	1/3	1/5	1/5	5	11/5
Social vs Environmental	1/3	1/3	1/3	1/5	1	4/9
Social vs Legal	1/5	3	1/3	1/7	5	13/4
Social vs Architectural	1/3	5	1/3	1/3	3	14/5
Social vs Cultural	3	3	1	1	3	21/5
Technological vs Environmental	3	5	3	3	1/5	25/6
Technological vs Legal	1	7	3	1/3	3	27/8
Technological vs Architectural	1/3	1	3	5	1/3	2
Technological vs Cultural	3	3	5	5	1/3	31/4
Environmental vs Legal	1/3	5	1/3	1/3	5	21/5
Environmental vs Architectural	1/3	3	1/3	1/5	1	1
Environmental vs Cultural	3	3	3	3	1/3	21/2
Legal vs Architectural	3	1/3	1/5	3	1/5	11/3
Legal vs Cultural	4	1/3	3	3	1/3	21/7
Architectural vs Cultural	7	3	3	3	3	34/5
2nd level						
Cost vs Local Economy	3	7	1	5	1/5	31/4
Cost vs Market Potential	1/3	5	1	1/5	1/3	13/8
Local Economy vs Market Potential	1/5	1	1	1/7	5	11/2
Social Impact vs Accessibility	1/3	1/5	1/3	1/3	5	11/4
Environmental impact vs Indoor Environmental Quality	1/3	1/3	1/5	1/3	5	11/4

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Flexibility and Adaptability vs Durability and Quality	1/3	1/5	1	1/3	1	4/7
Flexibility and Adaptability vs Physical characteristics	3	1/3	3	1/5	1/3	1 3/8
Durability and Quality vs Physical characteristics	1/5	3	1/3	3	1/3	1 3/8
Architectural value vs Cultural value	3	3	1	5	1/3	2 1/2

Compute the criterion weights

The weights of the objectives and criteria are weighted according to Formula 5. First, the weights are normalized with the columns, and then the normalized weights are aggregated to get one comprehensive weight for the criteria and objectives. The results of the normalized and aggregated weights are found in Table 12

Table 12: The normalized and aggregated criterion weights

Criteria	Weights	Objectives	Weights	Final weight
Political	0.15	A) Political and Community Support	1	0.15
Economic	0.24	B) Cost	0.50	0.12
		C) Local Economy	0.25	0.06
		D) Market Potential	0.25	0.06
Social	0.11	E) Social Impact	0.55	0.0605
		F) Accessibility	0.45	0.0495
Technological	0.16	G) Building Technology	1	0.16
Environmental	0.11	H) Environmental Impact	0.55	0.0605
		I) Indoor Environmental Quality	0.45	0.0495
Legal	0.08	J) Rules and Regulations	1	0.08
Architectural / physical	0.11	K) Flexibility and Adaptability	0.30	0.033
		L) Durability and Quality	0.43	0.0473
		M) Physical Characteristics	0.26	0.0286
Cultural	0.04	N) Architectural Value	0.71	0.0284
		O) Historic and Cultural value	0.29	0.0116

Checking the consistency

After the normalized and aggregated weights are determined for all objectives, the consistency can be checked. The Consistency Ratio is calculated using formula 6. When the CR falls below 0.10, it signifies a reasonable level of consistency in the judgments provided. Conversely, if the CR exceeds 0.10, it indicates inconsistent judgments. None of the pairwise comparison matrices had an inconsistency ratio above 0.10 which indicates that the stakeholder judgements were consistent.

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4.2.3. Step 6: Decide on the most appropriate circular adaptive reuse scenario

Define the decision matrix

Following the pairwise comparison from the stakeholders the decision matrix can be drawn up. In the case of the adaptive reuse scenarios, the decision matrix consists of 15 objectives each with a qualitative variant of strong, medium, or weak. Each row represents a scenario and each column represents an objective (Table 13):

Table 13: The decision matrix for the default scenarios

	A) Political and Community support	B) Cost	C) Local Economy	D) Market Potential	E) Social Impact	F) Accessibility	G) Building Technology	H) Environmental Impact	I) Indoor Environmental Quality	J) Rules and Regulations	K) Flexibility and Adaptability	L) Durability and Quality	M) Physical Characteristics	N) Architectural Value	O) Historic and Cultural Value
Scenario 1	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak
Scenario 17	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Strong	Strong	Strong	Weak	Weak
Scenario 148	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Strong	Strong	Strong	Medium	Medium	Strong	Medium	Medium	Weak
Scenario 170	Medium	Medium	Weak	Strong	Weak	Weak	Strong	Medium	Strong	Medium	Strong	Medium	Medium	Weak	Weak
Scenario 174	Weak	Strong	Medium	Strong	Medium	Medium	Medium	Strong	Medium	Weak	Strong	Weak	Medium	Weak	Weak
Scenario 119	Weak	Medium	Strong	Strong	Strong	Medium	Weak	Weak	Strong	Weak	Weak	Strong	Weak	Strong	Medium
Scenario 121	Medium	Strong	Strong	Strong	Weak	Medium	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Strong	Strong	Medium	Medium	Medium
Scenario 140	Medium	Weak	Medium	Weak	Weak	Strong	Strong	Strong	Strong	Strong	Weak	Medium	Weak	Strong	Weak
Scenario 168	Medium	Strong	Medium	Strong	Weak	Weak	Strong	Medium	Strong	Medium	Strong	Medium	Medium	Weak	Weak
Scenario 24	Medium	Medium	Strong	Medium	Weak	Weak	Medium	Weak	Weak	Weak	Strong	Strong	Strong	Strong	Strong
Scenario 45	Medium	Strong	Medium	Medium	Strong	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Strong	Strong	Medium	Strong	Strong
Scenario 29	Strong	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Medium	Strong	Weak	Medium	Strong	Medium	Strong	Strong	Strong	Strong
Scenario 68	Medium	Strong	Strong	Medium	Medium	Strong	Weak	Weak	Weak	Weak	Strong	Strong	Weak	Strong	Strong
Scenario 3	Strong	Weak	Strong	Strong	Strong	Strong	Strong	Strong	Strong	Strong	Strong	Strong	Strong	Strong	Strong
Scenario 33	Strong	Strong	Strong	Strong	Strong	Strong	Medium	Strong	Strong	Strong	Strong	Strong	Medium	Strong	Strong

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Transform the decision matrix into a fuzzy decision matrix - Fuzzification

After the decision matrix has been defined, the matrix can be transformed into a fuzzy decision matrix. In order for the linguistic variables to be transformed into fuzzy numbers, a conversion matrix can be used (Table 4). The fuzzy numbers represent a minimum value, a maximum value, and the most common value. After the conversion, the fuzzy decision matrix can be found in Table 14.

Table 14: The Fuzzy decision matrix for the default scenarios

	A)			B)			C)			D)			E)			F)			G)			H)			I)			J)			K)			L)			M)			N)			O)														
Scenario 1	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5			
Scenario 17	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5			
Scenario 148	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	3	5	7	3	5	7	5	7	9	3	5	7	3	5	7	3	5	7	3	5	7	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5			
Scenario 170	3	5	7	3	5	7	1	3	5	5	7	9	1	3	5	1	3	5	5	7	9	3	5	7	5	7	9	3	5	7	5	7	9	3	5	7	5	7	9	3	5	7	3	5	7	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5			
Scenario 174	1	3	5	5	7	9	3	5	7	5	7	9	3	5	7	3	5	7	3	5	7	5	7	9	3	5	7	1	3	5	5	7	9	1	3	5	3	5	7	1	3	5	3	5	7	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5			
Scenario 119	1	3	5	3	5	7	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	3	5	7	1	3	5	1	3	5	5	7	9	1	3	5	1	3	5	5	7	9	1	3	5	5	7	9	1	3	5	5	7	9	3	5	7	3	5	7			
Scenario 121	3	5	7	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	1	3	5	3	5	7	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	5	7	9	5	7	9	3	5	7	3	5	7	3	5	7	3	5	7	3	5	7			
Scenario 140	3	5	7	1	3	5	3	5	7	1	3	5	1	3	5	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	1	3	5	3	5	7	1	3	5	5	7	9	1	3	5	5	7	9	1	3	5			
Scenario 168	3	5	7	5	7	9	3	5	7	5	7	9	1	3	5	1	3	5	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	3	5	7	5	7	9	3	5	7	5	7	9	3	5	7	3	5	7	1	3	5	1	3	5						
Scenario 24	3	5	7	3	5	7	5	7	9	3	5	7	1	3	5	1	3	5	3	5	7	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9
Scenario 45	3	5	7	5	7	9	3	5	7	3	5	7	5	7	9	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	3	5	7	5	7	9	3	5	7	5	7	9	5	7	9
Scenario 29	5	7	9	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	3	5	7	5	7	9	1	3	5	3	5	7	5	7	9	3	5	7	5	7	9	3	5	7	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9
Scenario 68	3	5	7	5	7	9	5	7	9	3	5	7	3	5	7	5	7	9	1	3	5	3	5	7	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	1	3	5	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9
Scenario 3	5	7	9	1	3	5	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9
Scenario 33	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	3	5	7	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9	3	5	7	5	7	9	5	7	9	5	7	9

Normalize the decision matrix

To normalize the fuzzy numbers the following formula is used:

$$x_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij} - \min(x_j)}{\max(x_j) - \min(x_j)} \quad (16)$$

This means that the fuzzy numbers in the: maximum/minimum/most common column (see Table 12) are normalized based on the highest value within that column.

Construct the weighted normalized decision matrix

To form the weighted matrix the weights from step 5 are multiplied with the normalized fuzzy numbers to generate the weighted normalized decision matrix. This resulted in the following weighted normalized decision matrix (Table 16):

Determine Fuzzy Ideal and Negative-Ideal Solutions

In order to rank the scenarios in the Fuzzy TOPSIS method the FPIS (Fuzzy Positive Ideal Solution) and the FNIS (Fuzzy Negative Ideal Solution) need to be determined. The alternative closest to the FPIS and farthest from the FNIS is considered the best option. The FPIS represents an ideal solution where each objective is at its optimal fuzzy value. Conversely, the FNIS represents the least desirable outcomes, with each objective at its least advantageous fuzzy value. These concepts are constructed by identifying the best and worst possible fuzzy scores across all alternatives for each criterion. The FPIS and FNIS are calculated using formulas 10 and 11 and can be found in Table 17.

Calculate the Distance to Ideal Solutions:

The distances from each scenario to the FPIS (d_i^*) and FNIS (d_i^-) are calculated using the fuzzy distance measure which in this case is the Euclidian distance. The formulas for these distances, using the Euclidean distance can be found in section 3.4.2. Using these distances, each scenario's relative closeness to the ideal solution is calculated, which is used to rank the scenarios. The scenario with the shortest distance to the FPIS and the longest distance from the FNIS is considered the optimal choice. The distances to the FPIS and the FNIS can be found in Table 18

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Table 15: The weighted and normalized decision matrix for the default scenarios

		Scenario 1	Scenario 17	Scenario 148	Scenario 170	Scenario 174	Scenario 119	Scenario 121	Scenario 140	Scenario 168	Scenario 24	Scenario 45	Scenario 29	Scenario 68	Scenario 3	Scenario 33
A)	L	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.05	0.02	0.02	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.08	0.05	0.08	0.08
	M	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.08	0.05	0.05	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.12	0.08	0.12	0.12
	H	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.12	0.08	0.08	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.15	0.12	0.15	0.15
B)	L	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.04	0.07	0.04	0.07	0.01	0.07	0.04	0.07	0.01	0.07	0.01	0.07
	M	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.07	0.09	0.07	0.09	0.04	0.09	0.07	0.09	0.04	0.09	0.04	0.09
	H	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.09	0.12	0.09	0.12	0.07	0.12	0.09	0.12	0.07	0.12	0.07	0.12
C)	L	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.03
	M	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.03	0.02	0.05	0.05	0.05
	H	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.06	0.05	0.03	0.06	0.06	0.06
D)	L	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.03
	M	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.02	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.05
	H	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.03	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.03	0.05	0.06	0.06
E)	L	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.03
	M	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.05	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.05
	H	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.06	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.06	0.03	0.05	0.06	0.06
F)	L	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.03
	M	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.04
	H	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.05
G)	L	0.02	0.02	0.09	0.09	0.05	0.02	0.02	0.09	0.09	0.05	0.02	0.09	0.02	0.09	0.05
	M	0.05	0.05	0.12	0.12	0.09	0.05	0.05	0.12	0.12	0.09	0.05	0.12	0.05	0.12	0.09
	H	0.09	0.09	0.16	0.16	0.12	0.09	0.09	0.16	0.16	0.12	0.09	0.16	0.09	0.16	0.12
H)	L	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.03
	M	0.02	0.02	0.05	0.03	0.05	0.02	0.02	0.05	0.05	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.05
	H	0.03	0.03	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.03	0.03	0.06	0.06	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.06	0.06
I)	L	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.03	0.03
	M	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.04	0.04
	H	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.03	0.05	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.05	0.05

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Table 16: The results of the FPIS for the default scenarios

FPIS	Scenario 1	Scenario 17	Scenario 148	Scenario 170	Scenario 174	Scenario 119	Scenario 121	Scenario 140	Scenario 168	Scenario 24	Scenario 45	Scenario 29	Scenario 68	Scenario 3	Scenario 33
A)	0.00	0.01	0.07	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.01	0.04	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00
B)	0.02	0.02	0.08	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.08	0.03	0.02	0.00	0.08	0.00	0.08	0.02
C)	0.04	0.04	0.11	0.11	0.06	0.02	0.05	0.09	0.09	0.05	0.06	0.11	0.05	0.08	0.07
D)	0.04	0.04	0.11	0.08	0.05	0.02	0.05	0.11	0.08	0.06	0.06	0.11	0.06	0.08	0.07
E)	0.04	0.04	0.11	0.11	0.06	0.02	0.07	0.11	0.11	0.07	0.05	0.11	0.06	0.08	0.07
F)	0.04	0.04	0.11	0.11	0.07	0.04	0.07	0.09	0.11	0.08	0.08	0.10	0.06	0.09	0.08
G)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.03
H)	0.04	0.04	0.08	0.09	0.05	0.05	0.07	0.08	0.08	0.07	0.07	0.11	0.06	0.08	0.07
I)	0.04	0.04	0.09	0.09	0.07	0.03	0.08	0.09	0.09	0.08	0.08	0.10	0.08	0.09	0.08
J)	0.03	0.03	0.08	0.08	0.07	0.04	0.07	0.06	0.08	0.06	0.07	0.06	0.07	0.06	0.06
K)	0.05	0.04	0.11	0.10	0.07	0.06	0.07	0.12	0.10	0.07	0.07	0.11	0.07	0.10	0.09
L)	0.04	0.03	0.09	0.10	0.07	0.03	0.06	0.10	0.10	0.06	0.06	0.09	0.06	0.09	0.08
M)	0.05	0.04	0.11	0.11	0.08	0.06	0.08	0.12	0.11	0.07	0.08	0.11	0.09	0.11	0.10
N)	0.05	0.05	0.11	0.12	0.09	0.05	0.08	0.11	0.12	0.07	0.07	0.11	0.07	0.11	0.10
O)	0.06	0.06	0.12	0.12	0.09	0.06	0.09	0.12	0.12	0.08	0.09	0.12	0.09	0.12	0.11
di*	0.53	0.51	1.38	1.32	0.89	0.52	0.88	1.31	1.27	0.84	0.89	1.31	0.86	1.17	1.04

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Table 17: The results of the FNIS for the default scenarios

FNIS	Scenario 1	Scenario 17	Scenario 148	Scenario 170	Scenario 174	Scenario 119	Scenario 121	Scenario 140	Scenario 168	Scenario 24	Scenario 45	Scenario 29	Scenario 68	Scenario 3	Scenario 33
A)	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.08	0.05	0.05	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.11	0.08	0.11	0.11
B)	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.07	0.09	0.06	0.09	0.04	0.09	0.07	0.09	0.04	0.09	0.04	0.09
C)	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.01	0.04	0.04	0.04
D)	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.04	0.04
E)	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.01	0.03	0.04	0.04
F)	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.03
G)	0.06	0.06	0.12	0.12	0.09	0.05	0.05	0.12	0.12	0.09	0.05	0.12	0.05	0.12	0.08
H)	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.04	0.04
I)	0.01	0.01	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.03	0.03
J)	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.06	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.05	0.02	0.05	0.05
K)	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02
L)	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03
M)	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01
N)	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
O)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
di-	0.31	0.36	0.48	0.54	0.52	0.45	0.47	0.55	0.59	0.52	0.43	0.48	0.47	0.61	0.62

Compute the Closeness Coefficient

In the fuzzy TOPSIS method, the closeness indicator is a key metric used to rank the scenarios based on their proximity to the ideal solution. It quantifies how close each scenario is to the Fuzzy Positive Ideal Solution (FPIS) and how far it is from the Fuzzy Negative Ideal Solution (FNIS). This indicator is measured using the formula:

$$CI_i = \frac{d_i^-}{d_i^* + d_i^-} \tag{17}$$

The Closeness Coefficient for each scenario can be found in Table 16.

Rank the scenarios

After the Closeness Coefficient is calculated for all scenarios the ranking can be performed. Ultimately the scenario with the highest Closeness Coefficient best aligns with the preferences of the stakeholders. The scenario with the highest CC_i value is ranked as the best choice, as it strikes the optimal balance between maximizing desirable traits and minimizing undesirable ones, according to the objectives established in the decision matrix. The results of the final ranking can be found in Table 19. Based on the input of the stakeholders, scenario **119** is found to be the most appropriate option.

Table 18: The closeness coefficient and the final rank of the scenarios

Scenario	Closeness Coefficient (CC)	Rank
Scenario 1	0.3697664	5
Scenario 17	0.4107238	2
Scenario 148	0.2582244	15
Scenario 170	0.2905294	13
Scenario 174	0.3690793	6
Scenario 119	0.4602083	1
Scenario 121	0.345408	8
Scenario 140	0.2935847	12
Scenario 168	0.3183301	11
Scenario 24	0.3807852	3
Scenario 45	0.3276458	10
Scenario 29	0.2688563	14
Scenario 68	0.3529418	7
Scenario 3	0.3411472	9
Scenario 33	0.372032	4

5. Integration with CPIM

At the center of the Reincarnate project stands the CP-IM (Circular Potential – Information Management). In this tool, the ten innovations of the Reincarnate project come together trying to remove the bottlenecks in current practice with respect to collecting and tracing information about construction and demolition waste, avoiding CDW in the first place, and being able to reuse CDW in high product quality. In this paragraph, the potential (data) integration of deliverable 3.1 into the CP-IM will be elaborated on. When it comes to the proposed decision-making framework for the adaptive refurbishment and renovation of real estate assets, the three decision-making levels each have their own potential areas of data integration.

5.1. 1st level decision-making framework

For the 1st level decision-making framework, 3 relevant areas for data integration can be established: Condition, Utilization, and Collective utility:

5.1.1. Condition

The condition assessment is based on the criteria in the IconCUR model and comprises of 3 criteria (design standard, maintained service level, and regulatory compliance) assessed for 5 building elements: structure, exterior envelope, interior finishes, engineering services, and external works. For the ease of use of the decision-making framework, the building condition is assessed through a survey, in which expert knowledge can be elicited to arrive quickly at an initial intervention direction (appendix 1). However, the logic of the framework leaves room for a more detailed conditions assessment of the building that can be specified to the requirement of a specific region. An example of this is the use of the method proposed in the Dutch NEN276724 standard depicted in Figure 45. This standard provides an objective evaluation of the physical condition of an asset. The condition classification for each element is determined by the severity, intensity, and extent of defects aggregated into a class number. The condition class can deliver fact-based data to managers, enabling them to distinguish between medium- and long-term maintenance measures in relationship to the desired level of maintenance. This assessment method allows inspectors to efficiently gather data on the individual component level, which could be aggregated to a building level (or even portfolio level).

D 3.1 Circular decision-making for adaptive refurbishment and renovation of real estate assets

RE OnSite, an assessment application within the RE-Suite solution from Reincarnate partner Demo BV, already plays a crucial role in assisting inspectors to conduct on-site [non-destructive] condition assessments based on the method proposed in Dutch NEN2767, which makes it relatively easy to integrate this data into the CP-IM. When the data on the condition and relevant visual information of the defects of the elements of the building is already available through RE OnSite, this data could be extracted and integrated into the 1st level decision-making framework to establish a first intervention direction. Another methodology that can be used for the condition assessment is the Implementation guidelines of INSITER 8-step methodology addressing critical architectural/ structural components in existing buildings, from deliverable 1.3 of the INSITER European Union's H2020 project⁹. In this hands on 8-step implementation guideline, construction workers are provided with a self-inspection tool to capture the condition

Figure 43: On site condition assesment (deliverable 1.1)

of the building and building products

⁹ <https://www.insiter-project.eu/en/research-results/Pages/D1-3.aspx>

5.1.2. Utilization & collective utility

When it comes to the data integration possibilities of the utilization and collective utility criteria, no direct data automation possibilities might be found, but the data available in the RE-Suite software can be used to support expert judgment through the survey. Table 20 shows the criteria for utilization and collective utility and the potential for data extraction from the RE-Suite software:

Table 19: data integration possibilities 1st level decision-making framework

Criteria	Data available in RE-SUITE	Data placeholder in place	Data placeholder candidate to add	Data not available
Operational viability (economic, cultural, environmental)			X	
Locational context (economic, cultural, environmental)		X		
Risk and opportunity (economic, cultural, environmental)		X		
Asset valuation (economic, cultural, environmental)	X			
Profile / mission (economic, cultural, environmental)			X	
Demand / relevance (structure ,exterior envelope etc.)				X
Fitness for purpose ((structure ,exterior envelope etc.)			X	
User satisfaction (structure ,exterior envelope etc.)		X		

5.2. 2nd level decision-making framework

When it comes to the data integration possibilities for the 2nd level decision-making framework, a potential for further enhancement of the decision-making framework can be observed. The current decision on the most appropriate circular adaptive reuse scenario is based on fuzzy logic. For all scenarios descriptors three different potential variants are created that describe the possible future directions of the descriptor. These variants are qualitatively described, which makes them suitable for a fuzzy decision-making model like the Fuzzy TOPSIS model. To arrive

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at the most appropriate scenario, only the preferences of the stakeholders are needed through pairwise comparison as well as the fuzzy number ranges for the variants, which leaves little room for data integration. However, although not included in this deliverable, there is a possibility to extensively quantify the scenario based on actual performance, instead of qualitative variants. For this, a regular TOPSIS model could be used that ranks the scenarios based on actual data (An example of this model can be found in the BIMSpeed project's deliverable 7.1¹⁰). If this potential avenue for further enhancement of the model is followed, existing data from the RE-Suite software could be extracted for integration into the model. Table 20 shows the criteria for the 2nd level decision-making model and the potential for data extraction from the RE-Suite software:

Table 20: Data integration possibilities 2nd level decision-making framework

Criteria	Data available in RE-SUITE	Data placeholder in place	Data placeholder candidate to add	Data not available
Political support			X	
Stakeholder engagement			X	
Staff expertise			X	
project timeline and planning	X		X	
Ownership situation	X			
Adaptation/conversion cost		x		
Investment cost	x			
Maintenance cost	x			
Operational cost	x			
Life-cycle cost	x			
"Economic activity				x
Job creation				x
Public amenities				x
Location	x	X		
Target users	X	x		
Economic return	x	X		
Market value	x	x		
Financial risk		x		
Social cohesion			x	
Public spaces				x

¹⁰ <https://www.bim-speed.eu/en/results>

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Livability				x
Socio-economic conditions				x
"Vehicle accessibility			X	
Pedestrian accesibility			X	
Bicycle accessibility			X	
Public transport accesibility			X	
Wheelchair accessibility			X	
Parking facilities"			X	
(Renewable) energy system			X	
Electrical system			X	
Water system			X	
Security system			X	
HVAC	X			
System Integration			X	
Embodied energy			X	
Operational energy			X	
Water consumption			X	
pollution and waste			X	
Nature and biodiversity			X	
Air quality			X	
Ventilation capacity			X	
Thermal comfort			X	
Acoustics			X	
Visual comfort (lighting)			X	
Zoning regulations			X	
Urban masterplan regulations	x			
Heritage regulations				
Occupational health and well-being regulations			X	
Fire safety	x			
Design regulations			X	
Space/layout flexibility			X	
Flexibility of service ducts and corridors			X	
Dismount ability			X	
Climate adaptation measures			X	
Structural integrity		X		

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Material durability		x		
Robustness				x
Load bearing capacity				x
Floor area	x			
Construction type	x			
Floor height			X	
Plot size	x			
Building extendability			X	
Building coverage ratio			X	
Overall aesthetics of the building			X	
Authenticity				x
Architectural integrity				x
Architectural heritage preservation		X		
Design quality / human scale				x
Sense of identity				x
Educational Value				x
Cultural value		X		
Historic value		X		

5.3. 3rd level decision-making framework

For the product-level decision-making framework, most of the information assessment is based on expert judgment and is hard to standardize or automate within the CP-IM. However, for most questions in the 3rd level decision-making framework information on the condition of the building products is needed. As stated above, RE OnSite already assists inspectors in conducting on-site condition assessments based on the method proposed in Dutch NEN2767, based on the individual product level. Where for the 1st level decision-making framework data can be aggregated, for the 2nd level decision-making framework the segregated product data can be helpful for answering the questions. Although expert judgment is still needed to answer the questions in the model, there is a possibility to extract RE OnSite data on the condition of building products that can support stakeholders in making decisions.

6. Implementation on Reincarnate demonstration projects

The decision-making framework outlined in this report will be implemented to support the selection of the most appropriate intervention scenario in selected Reincarnate demonstration sites. Table. presents the characterization of four dedicated demonstration cases in which the innovation: strategic circular decision-making for real estate assets, will be implemented. For the selection of the demonstration cases for this innovation, the four quadrants of the 1st level decision-making framework were taken: Retain, Adaptive Reuse, Renovation, and Deconstruction. For the *Retain* demonstration example, only the first-level decision-making framework will be demonstrated, for the *Deconstruct* demonstration example, the first and third-level decision-making frameworks will be demonstrated, and for the *Renovation* and *Adaptive Reuse* demonstration examples, the whole decision-making framework will be demonstrated. All four demonstration cases intend to involve relevant stakeholders in the decision-making process such as architects, building owners, building users, and facility managers to develop scenarios and go through the decision-making frameworks.

Table 21: Reincarnate demonstration case characterization

Demonstration case	Location	Demonstration case owner/contact partner	Intended demonstration
3L Office Building (Retain)	Menden (Germany)	3L	1 st level decision-making framework
Apartment Building Paris Habitat (Renovation)	Paris (France)	Paris Habitat	The whole decision-making framework inc. scenario development
Kathreiner Haus (Adaptive Reuse)	Berlin (Germany)	TUB	The whole decision-making framework inc. scenario development
Lagemaat building (Deconstruction)	The Netherlands	Lagemaat	1 st and 3 rd level decision-making frameworks

7. Conclusion

This report presents a comprehensive circular decision-making framework tailored for the adaptive refurbishment and renovation of real estate assets. The framework integrates theoretical concepts with a practical implementation example to guide stakeholders in making informed decisions about the future use of buildings. The decision-making framework for the adaptive refurbishment and renovation of real estate assets provides a systematic approach to guide asset managers and building owners in exploring and implementing circular adaptive reuse scenarios. By structuring the decision-making process across three distinct levels, this framework facilitates the identification and selection of the most appropriate interventions for functionally obsolete buildings. The first level of the framework involves a thorough assessment of the building's current condition, utilization, and potential reward, leading to an initial intervention direction. This ensures that stakeholders are guided towards either adaptive reuse, renovation, or product-level decision-making frameworks based on the building's characteristics. At the second level, stakeholders refine their intervention choices by selecting and prioritizing objectives and criteria that align with their project goals. They then develop or choose from predefined adaptive reuse scenarios, and quantify their preferences to rank these scenarios effectively. The third level focuses on determining the future of building products based on the chosen scenario. This involves setting requirements for which products remain in use and which need a new life, guided by a detailed product-level decision-making framework.

This report aims to support stakeholders by offering a stepwise process guideline, ensuring that the interventions are not only appropriate and effective but also aligned with circular economy principles. An implementation example is given in which 15 distinct circular adaptive reuse scenarios are developed that can serve as the default scenarios. The comprehensive framework presented enables informed decision-making, promoting sustainable and adaptive reuse of buildings, and ultimately contributing to reducing construction and demolition waste.

Future empirical testing, will provide the necessary data to validate and refine these methodologies. The planned demonstration projects will play a crucial role in illustrating the practical application and benefits of this framework in real-world scenarios. By fostering a circular economy approach within the construction industry, this deliverable aims to significantly reduce construction and demolition waste, extend the life cycle of buildings, and promote sustainable building practices.

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9. Appendix

9.1. [The first-level decision-making assessment worksheet¹¹](#)

9.2. [Scenario development workshop template¹¹](#)

9.3. [Detailed description for the default scenarios¹¹](#)

9.4. [Default scenarios for the ScenarioWizard software¹¹](#)

9.5. [Circular adaptive reuse scenario scorecards for the default scenarios¹¹](#)

9.6. [Workshop template for connecting scenarios to CBA strategies¹¹](#)

¹¹ <https://github.com/BrianvLaar98/Reincarnate-Deliverable-3.1>